

CHANGING PARADIGM IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION: A STUDY OF OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

by

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the study entitled “**CHANGING PARADIGM IN MANAGEMENT EDUCATION: A STUDY OF OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION**” submitted by **Dr NANDITA MISHRA** to SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY for the award of the Post- Doctoral Fellow is a Bonafide record of the research work carried out by her under my supervision and guidance. The content of the Report, in full or parts have not been submitted to any other institute or university for the award of any degree or diploma.

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Dr Nandita Mishra
PDF Scholar

SYNOPSIS

India has a rich tradition of education and learning right from ancient times and especially during the Renaissance period, the Golden Age of Indian Culture. The major three achievements in education, during this period were the decimal system, the great Sanskrit epics, and the contribution to the sciences of astronomy, mathematics, and metallurgy. The four Vedas, i.e., the Rigveda, Yajurveda, Samaveda, and the Atharvaveda were configured through ideals, practices, and conducts. The doctrine of action (Karma) occupies a very significant place in the Indian system of education and has evolved during the transition from ancient to modern education. Two methods of teaching were being practiced during the Vedic period. First, the verbal/oral method, and the second based on thinking (Chintan). Current higher education has shown trends of multidisciplinary approaches along similar lines. NEP 2020 also suggests a multidisciplinary approach. Bloom's Taxonomy defines three domains of learning, cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. The ancient education system is also based on the three domains, to develop higher-order learning by building up the lower-level cognitive skills.

The exploratory study based on secondary published research articles on the education system in India, seeks to interpret extant academic research on the relevance of the ancient education system in modern multidisciplinary education.

Ancient learning systems based on Vedas included many yogic practices. In general, to calm the mind and improve learning, asanas, chanting of mantras, and meditation were done. The same practices are emphasized by HEI, guided by UGC and AICTE. Universal Human value (UHV) has been implemented for all-around personality development and practice of an integrated approach in Yoga. Modern methods to develop memory include the logical method, spaced learning, and rational memory. All of these are derived from the ancient way of teaching and learning. Using the ABCD listing methodology this study explores the advantages, benefits, constraints and disadvantages in the modern education system, both from learners' view point and teachers' view point .

Objective of this study is to understand the role of the modern multidisciplinary education in outcome based education and how different is modern education from traditional conventional education. The basic focus of traditional education was passing information, skills, and practices to the next generation. Traditional education was based on customs, traditions, and religions. Modern education on the other hand is multidisciplinary and is based on knowledge-based society. The advancement of technology coupled with industry 4.0 has brought radical changes in the modern education system.

Case based learning, problem solving skills, simulation-based learning, experiential learning, role play and project – based learning are some innovative teaching pedagogies, to be implemented early in the education system to develop outcome-based education for better employability. The study shows that modern multidisciplinary learning pedagogy is imperative for higher education. Integrating the concept of multidisciplinary learning and modern learning pedagogy can address the differences in the learning style of students and improve their employability skills. The techniques like case-based learning, experiential learning, project-based learning, and role play motivate students to think and link theory to real life situations.

Multidisciplinary education also helps to provide freedom to explore knowledge and choose courses by choice.

The current mandate of the New Education Policy 2020, is preparing students for the evolving industry practices and skills. Academic qualifications alone through curriculum is not sufficient to adapt in the VUCA world. Extracurricular activities coupled with co-curricular activities can enforce all round personality development of students. Extracurricular activities make the learner mentally agile, participative, responsive, confident, and independent. An illustration through a case in point enables understanding the importance of extracurricular activities and how they prove to be beneficial for learners in the higher education system.

The analysis shows that both extra-curricular and curricular activities contribute towards confidence building, along with development of knowledge, skills, and attitude

With current mandate of skill India mission and developing youth for Industry 4.0, to match the skills required in the ever-changing requirement, this paper will contribute to the understanding, how the skills can be developed for the learners in Higher Education.

Mental wellbeing refers to an individual's beliefs and values, often related to a higher power or a sense of purpose. Mental wellbeing and sustainability are two distinct but related concepts. Research has shown a positive relationship between an individual's mental wellbeing orientation and support for sustainable practices. For example, Dhiman (2016) argued that the preservation of the inviolability of the planet is only possible if the individual's life is based on moral and spiritual awareness. Further, "there is no sustainability without wellbeing. interactions can contribute towards mental wellbeing.

This research study draws attention to the role and importance of mental health in higher education and suggests implementation and integration strategies of mental wellbeing in higher education. Mental health concerns all, children, adults, students, employees and every human being. The 17 SDGs on eradicating poverty, preventing conflicts and disasters, promoting education, providing decent livelihoods and standard of living, partnership and collaboration, will not be successful unless we prioritize the overall wellbeing, which includes mental wellbeing. Poor mental health and unfulfilled human potentials are worrisome as they stand as obstacles to attain the SDGs.

A state of wellbeing where individuals realize their potential, can cope with normal challenges in life, can work productively and contribute towards CSR activities will only help organizations and nations achieve the Sustainable development goals by 2023.

After liberalization of the Indian economy, the impact of privatisation, economic changes, and international markets had put pressure on all functions of the organizations (Bhatnagar , 2007; Budhwar, et al, 2026) There is a requirement amongst the managers to build capacities, and competencies and capabilities. With the overall competition, retaining and attracting good talent has become a challenge. Employee engagement is key to the retention of talent in an organization. Over the last few years, several studies related to the management of talent has been conducted, but mostly in developed countries and in a corporate context. Even within the employee engagement framework, very little has been done on teaching faculty and staff in colleges and universities.

There is an immense need to study faculty engagement in the education sector. The literature study on employee engagement shows very little study in faculty engagement and motivation. Faculty engagement and motivation is possible if organizations, i.e. colleges and institutes

provide the teachers with a passion to work and an engaging ambience which their performances and gives them a continuous satisfying work experience.

The effectiveness of higher education system depends on effective and vibrant teachers with knowledge of Academics, Assessment and evaluation, Pedagogy, Research Culture, and Innovation in teaching & learning. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 specifies that the “most important factor in the success of higher education institutions is the quality and engagement of its faculty. The study focuses on the understanding of NEP and Outcome Based Education amongst faculty members and academic leaders, the factors affecting teaching and learning in higher education, and the role of academic leadership in implementing outcome-based education in higher education. Performance improvement helps the organization to meet its goals and objectives. Performance counselling is a very important activity that helps employees to know themselves better. It has been observed that employee engagement increases with performance counselling. Hence the desired result of NEP implementation will be better with faculty training and counselling. The attributes of Academic Leadership for academic, administrative, and research & extension activities are identified, analyzed, and evaluated. A conceptual model with the required attributes and qualities for a Role model/Super academic leader is suggested in the study

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Management education is an important branch of higher education in India and has a high impact on India's economic growth. It has proven to be very successful in providing much-needed qualified and skilled professional manpower. The NEP's focus on multidisciplinary education in management institutions suggested future policy implementation and a road map for management education. Unlike other disciplines, management schools do not have the intake of bachelor students from their disciplines only. The postgraduate courses offered by the management institutes in India have interest of students from diverse backgrounds. The management institutes provide holistic education within multiple fields of management. Almost 82 % of seats in postgraduate management courses are occupied by students from diverse educational backgrounds. Thus, management schools have a highly multidisciplinary student intake compared to other disciplines.

By their very nature, business schools are different from other educational institutions and thus need to be looked at differently by policymakers. Management education is highly linked to the industry's requirements, and the coursework can be flexible. Globally and in India, management schools are focused on the postgraduate program while accepting students from all disciplines.

It is heartening that the Ministry of Human Resources has developed the National Education Policy, also called the New Education Policy, NEP 2020. NEP 2020 is aimed to address and plug the various loopholes in the current education system. NEP mentions the need for entrepreneurship education and industry-institute partnerships at multiple levels of the academic hierarchy. NEP emphasizes research, innovation, entrepreneurship, and professional education, especially on the curriculum with learning outcomes like knowledge, skills, self-confidence, and entrepreneurial initiatives.

Business schools have provided professionally trained graduates to Industry 4.0 to fulfil its requirements. What's turning out to be more important is the approach in the face of the complex challenges and uncertainties. The administrative abilities of leaders and managers are put to the test only in complex situations. When companies redefine their purpose, B- Schools should redefine their pedagogy. The role of higher education and B- schools is imperative to rethink work, workforces, and workplaces. Skills required in 2019 are not the same anymore. Often, questions on problem-solving and perseverance are asked during recruitment. The answer to such questions is possible only when the students have exposure to industry-related activities and problem-solving skills integrated with the program and the course.

Academic institutions have sought to respond to the demand of changing and evolving environmental conditions and structural changes in higher education. The roles of the leaders

within the institutions have changed to solve different functional needs at the institute level. The role of an academic leader is managing through information, monitoring, disseminating knowledge, delegating, designing, discussing, making, distributing, and managing people by people, acting directly or indirectly. Economic and administrative responsibilities, human resource management and development, internal and external cooperation, networking, research collaboration, and many other roles have evolved in the last ten years. Today's B-School faculty has to spend time outside academics to impact career growth positively.

In today's scenario, the new employee is expected to deliver from day one of joining; hence, the learning period is considerably reduced. This also means the responsibility of the faculty in making the students job-ready is immense.

Diversity of thinking is much needed in a business school; academic leaders and faculty must develop a corporate outlook and mindset in students, which is achieved by making the academic industry goal-oriented. It can further be added here that setting goals like research, classroom teaching, institution building, and administrative responsibilities for faculty members in an agile business school is to update knowledge in management education, keeping up-to-date with the recent trends and requirements, and also competing for better ranking and quality management. It has also been observed that faculty handling varied roles as teachers and administrators make better academic leaders and develop the ability to tackle difficult situations, problems, and knowledge to achieve individual and institutional goals.

This edited book explores the different aspects of outcome-based education and emphasizes the role of faculty and academic leaders in transforming higher education.

The current circumstances of higher education give ample cause for alarm on many concerns and would require higher education experts to find out how such changes will affect the academic profession in the long term.

The study will be based on the data collected from three groups of people. The first set of academic leaders- from different management institutes, second set will be of management faculty from different management Institutes management students across the same management institutes. To have better results the study will be pan India based, covering East, West, North and South Data will be collected through a data triangulation approach. For the purpose, structured questionnaires will be used, telephonic interview of sample and also Focus Group Discussions with members from the three chosen categories will be conducted. The prospective participants will be contacted by the researcher and consent form will be obtained from all participants The study will employ three different methods of data collection, preliminary interview and Focus Group Discussions to yield the parameters on which a structured questionnaire will be prepared. After deciding on the constructs of the scale, indicator items will be prepared with the assistance of the experts in the field. Statistical analysis will be done using parametric and non- parametric test, wherever required. For the purpose of confidentiality, names of academic institutions, academic leaders, and faculty are not mentioned in the report.

This study explores outcome-based education with a focus on inputs (Students and Faculty), processes (systems and focus), and output (employability and outreach). The study explores how education has evolved since the beginning of the ancient education. Education in ancient India was quite different from the rest of the world. In old India, both formal and informal educational systems existed. India is a young country, and its demographic dividend is the force

behind its growth. Technological and scientific improvements have boosted economic growth in India. Indian university is the biggest and the most extensive education system built on the backbone and foundation of ancient education. The primary purpose of this study is to convey what is needed to develop our current education system, adapting from the ancient to the modern education system in a robust way. The National Education Policy 2020 envisages inclusive and equitable quality education while addressing the growing developmental imperatives of the country.

The research emphasizes the role of systems, policies, and procedures in fulfilling outcome-based education. Academic autonomy at the individual faculty level enhances performance outcomes. This can be extended at the student level through choice-based education. The performance Target of Faculty through the Appraisal system and students' performance through the mentoring system can enhance the quality of higher education in India.

CHAPTER 2

EVOLUTION OF EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION

A traditional education system is a customary form of education in which the main motive of the education system is to pass on knowledge to the future generation. The traditional education system is one in which information is acquired within the four walls of the classrooms. Education in ancient India was quite different from the rest of the world. The disciple or the learner had to leave the house and live with the teacher in a gurukul for the entire period of learning. The society or the kingdom couldn't interfere with the curriculum, teaching and learning. In ancient India, both formal and informal ways of education system existed. Education was imparted at home, in temples, in pathshalas and gurukuls. In the traditional education system, students were taught about traditions, customs, rituals, and religion. (Ghonge M, Bag R, Singh A (2020)[15]) Students learned more about custom, religion, dharma, truthfulness, discipline, self-reliance and more about nature and creation. As we progress, we see the education system has evolved. With the introduction of the modern education system, learners are able to access the current information and transition towards knowledge-based society. Modern-day education is more interdisciplinary and application oriented. The Indian education system is very popular and diversified among other countries education systems due to its adaptation from the ancient education system.

India is a young country, and the demographic dividend of India is the force behind the growth. Technological and scientific improvements have boosted economic growth in India. An Indian university is the biggest and the largest education system built on the backbone and foundation

of ancient education followed by education in the medieval period. The main purpose of this paper is to convey what is needed to develop in our current education system, adapting from the ancient education system to fit the modern education system in a robust way. The National Education Policy 2020 envisages inclusive and equitable quality education while addressing the growing developmental imperatives of the country.

Early childhood education in NEP 2020, focusses on developing, inquisitiveness, team work and collaboration among learners. The ancient education system also focuses on the same. The Higher Education Institutions emphasises on cross- functional and interdisciplinary learning approach (Aithal P.S & Aithal S (2020)[14]) We draw the corollary from ancient education.

The National Education Policy has placed special emphasis on the rich heritage of ancient Indian culture, taking Yoga, Ayurveda and Spiritualism as the guiding path and this has translated India today into the global power,(Khusnam P.N (2022)[16])

Changes in reforms are placed in such a way that learning outcomes bring highest quality equity and integrity into the system right from schooling to higher education. Just like the ancient education system modern education is multidisciplinary, cross- disciplinary and interdisciplinary. This paper is based on a systematic literature review of the ancient education system, adaptations in the medieval education system, education system from 1986 to 2020 and the current NEP 2020.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- (1) To study the evolution of ancient Indian education.
- (2) To identify specific features of the National Policy on Education-1968.
- (3) To understand the National Policy on education – 1986.
- (4) To evaluate the need for National Education policy 2020.
- (5) To compare ancient education system with the modern education system.
- (6) To analyse the role of ancient education system in the modern education system.
- (7) To suggest strategies for effective outcome based education in the modern system

3. EVOLUTION OF ANCIENT INDIAN EDUCATION:

3.1 Education during the Vedic period: 1500 BCE- 600 BCE: The ultimate aim of education emerged as the Chitti-Vritti-Nirodha (the control of mental activities connected with the practical world) Education was holistic and all-rounded. An attempt was made to make the student experience the situation or the divine truth and mould himself and society accordingly. The teacher and the student always shared very close relationship and transparency in their understanding. The teacher was considered as a role model because he was approved by the society in which the student lived. Through daily lectures and classes and practical work, teacher imparted vocational training and demonstrated dignity of labour. The basis of ancient education and Indian culture lies in the four Vedas.

The Rigvedic education was mainly meant for the priest class and there was secular religion and vocational trainings for the masses. The method of teaching was practical during the Vedic period and was based on Oral (Verbal) and Thinking (Chintan). In the modern days too, the teacher guides the students to research, apply, evaluate and create, this process was very much present during the Vedic period. The educational system of the Vedic period was mainly focussed on character formation, development of personality and to large extent through Yajurveda and Atharvaveda teaching, which made it practical and thus evolved the Aryan Culture. Hearing, thinking and meditation were the three principal methods of instructions. The question- answer system too evolved during the later period.

The teacher enjoyed a predominant place and was the greatest guide for the pupils. The rules of Conduct and Discipline was an inseparable aspect of education in those days the duration of Vedic education was twelve years and education were imparted through Gurukuls, Parishads (Academic Institutions) and Sammelans (Conferences). The modern education system also resonates with the same structure.

For the Vaishyas, i.e., the business class, agriculture, animal husbandry, and trade were their chief occupation. To understand business, a study of arithmetic, geography, economics, science of agriculture, and business method was extremely essential. There was no provision of higher education for the shudras. The shudras mainly learned dancing, vocal music, orchestral music and the art of dyeing. Their knowledge and skills were transferred from generation to generation (Indian Education System [9]).

The biggest demerit of the system was the watertight compartments in education and training, based on the caste system.

3.2 Education in the Sutras: 600 BCE – 200 BCE: The period of Vedic literature was followed by that of sutra literature. The need for education and training, during the Vedic period, gave rise to the Sutras education, which was a more towards practical method of education. One special feature of this education was the specialization branches of learning offered to the students. Many branches of knowledge, such as Geometry, Algebra, Physiology, Astronomy, Astrology, and Vedas reached the peak of learning. In the work of Panini, Katyayana, and Patanjali there is mention of this literature and work. One feature distinctly stood out during this period was the progress in philosophy. The sole objective of the entire system of education was character formation and personality development. This was achieved through, Yoga (Integration of mind and body), Nyaya (Justice), Karma (Deeds), and Vedanta (conclusion of Vedas).

3.3 Education in the Epics: The scattered facts in the epics, like Ramayana and Mahabharat, give us glimpses into military education during that period. The word Kulapati (Chancellor) and Upkulapati (Vice-Chancellor) in modern-day University structure is derived from the mention in the epics. Kulapati was applied to the Guru (head) of 10,000 disciples. Military science was generally called Dhanurveda. During this period military education science was very important. Many institutions such as Taxila, Ujjain, Nalanda, Banaras, and Madura were established. Jibaka, a well-known medical expert of the 6 Century, Panini the famous grammarian of the 7 Century, and Kautaliya, of the 4 Century, the authority on Arthasastra, were students of Taxila.

To summarise, education in the epics was mainly vocational training, essentially practical and application oriented.

3.4 National Policy on Education 1968: In the post-independence period a major concern of the Indian government was to given increasing attention to education. The education commission was set up in 1964- 66, was appointed to advise government on the national pattern of education and on the general principles and policies for the development of education. A sustained effort was made to raise the quality of education at all stages and emphasis on the development of science and technology and the cultivation of moral and social value. The government of India promoted and developed the following during 1968 (National Education Policy 1968 [8])

- (1) Free and Compulsory education up to the age of 14, under Article 45 of the Directive Principle of State Policy.
- (2) The academic freedom of teachers to pursue and publish independent studies and research, along with the teachers' emoluments and service conditions we also considered.
- (3) Development of languages like Hindi, Sanskrit, English, one South- Indian languages and one international language was also encouraged.
- (4) More emphasis on education of girls, tribal communities and physically and mentally challenged children were given.
- (5) Education was given in the field of science, with special emphasis on research in agriculture and industry.
- (6) The education structure was broadly uniform in all parts of the country.

Merits:

- (1) Compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 and emphasis also on adult education
- (2) Suitable programs were designed to reduce wastage and stagnation in schools, with suitable teacher education to improve teaching standards
- (3) The three language formula helped to develop proficiency and cultural integrity amongst the learners, the future of India

Demerits:

- (1) To many objectives and milestones to achieve in five -year time. No objectives or assignment could therefore focus on one task completion
- (2) Education is an extremely complex system and cannot be delivered by Central Government alone. The active role of State Government was missing in executing the NPE 1968
- (3) Education and research, both require high budget outlay. There were scarcity of resources in implementing the big national policy on education

3.5 The National Policy on Education -1986 : The essential focus on pre-primary education was required and the main components were health, nutrition , play- way method and establishing a home and community relationship to ensure higher enrolment ratio,(Gupta A (2022)[17]) NPE 1986,was intended to prepare India for the 21 Century. The policy emphasized the need for change, education in India during this time was at a crossroad. On one side there was an over growing population and on the other side there was requirement and need of practical education. While the education policy of 1968 was compulsory education, the major focus on 1986 National Policy on education was to overcome the disparity between diverse social group. It suggested 10+ 2+ 3 structure and gave autonomy to the syllabus followed by the states. There are 10 Core elements of the NPE 1986, India's common cultural heritage, democracy and secularism, protection of the environment, removal of social barriers, knowledge of India's freedom movement, constitutional obligation, nurturing national identity, population control, egalitarianism and gender equality, regarding women's equality.

Merits:

(1) Recognition of the importance of technical and management education, Expansion of technical education both at degree and diploma level. The emphasis was on the facilities and on quality management education and higher education keeping in mind the changing economic scenario

(2) Open and Distance Education to augment opportunities for higher education and making higher education cost effective and innovative

(3) The University system was also made centre stage, with focus on more universities in rural areas to improve knowledge creation and knowledge sharing in the rural population. Emphasis on agricultural universities to meet the need of research and development in agriculture for mitigating the food requirement and improving rural education.

Demerits:

(1) Not much uniformity was seen in the education system of the country. A core curriculum with multidisciplinary approach across all education and education level was overlooked

(2) Enrolment by itself is of little importance, if the student doesn't continue to study after one year. There was no proper mechanism to ensure that every child attended school regularly

(3) The challenge mentioned in point number 2 above could have been mitigated by mobilisation of teachers and local communities. The success of any strategy is judged by its implementation. A major challenge was this, given the teacher and student ratio.

3.6 The National Education Policy – 2020- If we look at the proposal made in 2019, we find that there was a plan for integrating vocational education and employability skills with regular education, of course in a phased manner. Skilling is no more a buzzword; it's the order of the day. The push is for a policy backed by skill development initiative to enhance employability. The skill report of 2019 says that 45.6 % of the youth graduating are employable and only 4.69 % of the workforce in India is skilled. Compared to this, 24% of the workforce is skilled in China, 52% in US, 68% in UK, 80% in Japan and 96% in South Korea. The percentage is low in India because the mismatch is between Skill Training and Employability (NEP 2020 [4-7])

Education should provide professionally trained graduates to Industry 4.0 to fulfill its requirements. What's turning out to be more important is the approach in the face of the complex challenges and uncertainties. The administrative abilities of leaders and managers are put to the test only in complex situations. When companies are redefining their purpose, education should redefine their pedagogy (Mishra N. (2020) [13]) To rethink work, workforces and workplaces, the role of higher education and B- schools, is imperative. Skills required in the year 2000 are not the same anymore. Often questions on problem-solving and perseverance are asked during recruitment. The answer to such questions is possible only when the students have exposure to industry-related activities and problem-solving skills, integrated with the programme and the course.

The technological disruption that the world is currently undergoing is unprecedented. This has led to a radical transformation in the education ecosystem. According to the Organization for Economic Development (OECD), "Future of Education and Skill Project (2030)", we need to

replace old education standards with an educational framework with the 21st century skills of creativity, critical thinking, communication, and collaboration. According to Mishra. N. (2020) [13], this can't be achieved by simply moving teaching from whiteboard to online. What is needed is radically transforming the way knowledge is disseminated and skills acquired. Along with knowledge and skills, what is needed is attitude and value to thrive in and shape the future to a more global workplace.

The FICCI- EY report, 2021 [1], has also studied the well-reasoned and bold reformation steps suggested by NEP 2020. The NEP focuses on disruptive changes by taking into cognizance the issues of equitability, inclusivity, accessibility, exploratory and experimental, all ingredients required for transforming Education 4.0 and beyond.

Curriculum and pedagogy could be revised to incorporate formal, informal, physical, and digital elements to enhance learning. Education models focussed on blended and interdisciplinary learning, that integrates technology access, teaching pedagogy and assessment methods can deliver better quality education.

In a country where 50 % of the population is below the age of 25 years, it's the onerous responsibility of the Government to provide better education, training and skill development to enable the youth for a proper livelihood. Our literacy rate of 74 % and in some states at 100% doesn't fulfil the requirement of skill needed by the industry.

Our focus was earlier on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy. In the current situation the focus should move to employability skill. With this background, certain changes in the NEP are proposed with the vision for balanced education. The focus of NEP 2020 has been, employability and entrepreneurship [18-21].

Merits:

(1) The objective of Nep 2020 is to provide multidisciplinary and interdisciplinary liberal education to everybody. Consolidation of existing fragmented HEIs into Multidisciplinary Universities and Multidisciplinary Autonomous Colleges with focus on research and teaching intensive colleges.

(2) Aiming to increase the Gross Enrolment Ratio in Higher Education including vocational education from 26.3 % in 2018 to 50 % in 2035. GER is not just enrolment and studying for one year, it ensures tracking education till completion

(3) The Academic Bank of Credit (ABC) which would digitally store the academic credits is another positive feature of the NEP 2020. The digital storage will allow flexibility for students to complete their Bachelor Degree, Master Degree and PhD degrees, with multiple exit options.

Demerits:

(1) Conversion of affiliated colleges into autonomous colleges might compromise with the, student-teacher ratio, infrastructure ratio, quality education and compliance. Granting autonomy to not so ready institutes might defeat the very purpose of NEP 2020

(2) Changing the mind-set of all stakeholders and administrators at the same time is very challenging. Faculty members with their varied role in education will now have to focus on outcome based and research oriented curriculum.

(3) Delay in decision making process as various lobbies will act in the system, this may affect the accreditation process, outcome based learning, standard benchmarks and awards

3.7 The Modern Education System based on Ancient Education System: It is important to improve modern education with its increasing levels of academic requirements. The literature analysis emphasizes that ancient learning systems based on Vedas included many yogic practices. In general, to calm the mind and improve learning, asanas, chanting of mantras, and meditation were done. The same practices are emphasized by HEI, guided by UGC and AICTE. Universal Human value (UHV) has been implemented for all-round personality development and practice of an integrated approach in Yoga. A 10-day UHV program has been made compulsory for all students during the orientation program. Modern methods to develop memory included the logical method, spaced learning, and rational memory. All of these are derived from the ancient way of teaching and learning.

4. RELEVANCE OF ANCIENT EDUCATION IN MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM :

Table 1: Comparison of ancient education model with modern education

Issue	Ancient Education	Modern education
Teaching	Instruction based	Discussion based
Learning	Passive learning attitude	Active learning attitude and high engagement
Role of Teachers	Instructor	Mentor
Learning Activities	Text-books and texts	Project-based learning
Learning Locations	Traditional classrooms or gurukuls	Large learning space, including internet
Teacher Training	Degrees, credentials, and certificates	Continuous training and upskilling
Industry's Perception of Graduates	Assembly line workers	Co-creators and entrepreneurs
Employability	Qualified and major focussed	Prepared for multiple careers
Result	Limited career prospects	Equipped with a variety of skills & multiple career paths

Adapted from <https://www.dreamformula.education/edu4>

5. ANALYSIS OF ANCIENT EDUCATION COMPARED TO MODERN EDUCATION:

In exploratory research, analysis refers to the process of examining and interpreting gathered information. Exploratory research is conducted when there is limited knowledge or understanding about a particular topic or problem, and its purpose is to gain insights, generate postulates, identify patterns or relationships, and generate new knowledge about a particular phenomenon or problem. There are many analysis frameworks used in scholarly research which include SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis [22], PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis [23], and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis [24].

Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages (ABCD) analysis framework in proposed in the year 2015 to analyze systems, concepts, ideas, strategies, products/services, materials, etc [25-26]. ABCD analysis framework can be used both qualitatively and quantitatively depending upon requirements [x4]. The qualitative ABCD analysis framework consists of (1) ABCD listing from information gathering from primary and secondary sources [27-35], (2) ABCD listing from Stakeholders' point of view of a system [36-40], (3) Factor and Elemental analysis using ABCD framework [41-46]. The quantitative ABCD analysis framework consists of (1) Ranking the ABCD constructs based on primary data [47-54], and (2) Statistical analysis of ABCD constructs. In this section, we have used ABCD listing from stakeholders' points of view (both learners and teachers) on ancient education compared to modern education in Higher Education.

5.1 ABCD Listing from Learners' Point of View:

(A) Advantages:

- (1) The teaching and learning discussions encourages high engagement of the learner.
- (2) Focus on learning is more project-based and practical.
- (3) Learning is more technology-driven and focuses on learning infrastructure.
- (4) Modern education is outcome-based and emphasizes on upskilling.
- (5) Multiple career opportunities provided by industry and economy.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Modern-day education is not class or occupation-based, its more merit-based.
- (2) Modern-day education is multi-disciplinary and open to all.
- (3) The benefits of education of NEP 2020 are balanced with academics, experiential and skill development.
- (4) Modern education is credit based on the advantage of an academic bank of credit.
- (5) Modern-day education (NEP 2020) is more flexible and allows students to pick and choose their academic journey.

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Modern day education is expensive and requires heavy investment.
- (2) Education is more technology-based, thereby posing a constraint for places with poor technology infrastructure.
- (3) There is a shortage of trained and skilled teachers in implementing the new curriculum.
- (4) Bureaucracy and red-tapes can delay the implementation process.
- (5) India's challenging situation on poverty eradication, unemployment, and healthcare reduces the focus on education.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) The focus on project-based experiential learning may reduce the impact of academic rigour.
- (2) Though education is skill-based the results are yet to materialize in the absence of trained teachers
- (3) The role of a teacher or mentor is relegated to a facilitator, thereby affecting discipline and respect, two important virtues for a successful career.
- (4) There is a loss of communication skills, peer learning, and teamwork as the results are individualistic and goal-oriented.
- (5) Due to excessive focus on technology, there is reduced social interaction.

5.2 ABCD Listing from Teachers' Point of View:

(A) Advantages :

- (1) Focus on research and innovation for teachers, thereby promoting more learning and development opportunities. With new focus on intellectual property rights teachers are more inclined towards innovation, patents and research papers
- (2) More opportunities for teachers with talents and skilled in managing higher education institutions. Small colleges will be transformed into cluster colleges and universities thus providing opportunities for teachers from smaller colleges to move to either research- intensive universities or teaching-intensive universities
- (3) Merit based appointment and promotion on the basis of Career Advancement System(CAS) to make NEP 2020 more effective by attracting and retaining good teaching and research talent. Faculty selection and promotion will therefore be more transparent
- (4) More flexibility to teachers with autonomy in curriculum designing, teaching and evaluation. This will enhance faculty engagement and improve the learning outcome

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Education leaders are recognised as role models and faculty at senior level are encouraged to continue research work along with administrative responsibilities,
- (2) Boosting online training and teaching (ICCT) , allowing faculty to undergo upskilling through MOOCS and Swayam courses
- (3) Flexibility to faculty in teaching across various different streams and specializations or choosing to teach one single area of expertise.
- (4) Opportunities for retired professors as research guides and welcoming industry practitioners as professor of practice to enhance experiential learning

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Teaching the fundamental subjects in mother –tongue can be a big constraint for many teachers
- (2) Multiple entry and exit route for learners might make it difficult for teachers to keep track and bring the learners to the next best level possible
- (3) Training teachers for multidisciplinary curriculum, examination reforms and changing the mind-set of all teachers to implement NEP 2020 comes with its own limitations and challenges
- (4) Along with the teaching load, which is the primary duty of any teacher, the focus has moved to research and innovation, this might be challenging to teachers without any institutional and domestic support.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) Faculty productivity might be challenging if too diverse and multidisciplinary education system is implemented.
- (2) Bringing uniformity in the education system will take time and hence the Academic Bank of Credit or transfer of credits will be a lengthy process
- (3) Education is a state subject, the willingness and preparedness of every state in achieving NEP 2020 could be different, as the NEP 2020 education system stresses on autonomy and flexibility
- (4) Influences & lobbies in the process of accreditation and approvals to attain full autonomy will defeat the very purpose of education and employability focus of NEP 2020 by diluting the standards and parameters of HEI.

6. SUGGESTIONS BASED ON ANALYSIS :

- (1) Modern-day education should aim at developing good, well-rounded creative, and ethical individuals, contributing productively to society.
- (2) Revamping the curriculum, pedagogy, assessments, teaching, and learning method to develop student-centric education.
- (3) Education should be more multidisciplinary and choice-based.
- (4) Focus should be made on faculty/teachers' training and upskilling to enable them to implement outcome-based education. This will allow autonomy and flexibility in teaching and research.
- (5) Effective regulatory system with good governance to assess the quality of education standards. Light but tight is what NEP 2020 mentions.

7. CONCLUSION :

A holistic and multidisciplinary education will help develop well-rounded individuals that possess critical 21st-century capacities in fields across the arts, humanities, languages, sciences, social sciences, and professional, technical, and vocational fields; an ethic of social engagement; soft skills, such as communication, discussion, and debate; and rigorous specialization in a chosen field or fields.

The influence of ancient education in the modern education system is tremendous. The emphasis on Indian Knowledge System, Value education, Yoga, and Skill based education is to develop psychological well-being through grit. The perceived grit in a person is highly influenced by psychological well-being, hence the focus on holistic education (Chakraborty et al (2020) [11]) Ancient education always focused on higher knowledge of self and knowledge of strength. Modern-day education emphasises on this concept of self-awareness and skill development through experiential and multidisciplinary learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] Higher Education in India: Vision 2040, ficci-hes.com/pdf/2021/eyreport.pdf, accessed on 26/02/2021
- [2] India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, <https://indianexpress.com>
- [3] [Indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilla/story/nep-2020](https://indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilla/story/nep-2020)
- [4] National Education Policy 2020, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India, www.niepid.nc.in/nep-2020.pdf, accessed on 02/08/2020
- [5] National Education Policy: Here” What are education experts saying about the new National Education Policy.” www.indiatoday.in/education-today
- [6] Salient- Features of NEP 2020, www.hindustantimes.com, accessed on 10/08/2020
- [7] Salient Features of NEP 2020, UGC, www.ugc.ac.in, accessed on 02/08/2020

- [8] The National Education policy 1968: [https:// www.education. gov. in](https://www.education.gov.in)
- [9] Indian Education System: An overview of the Ancient Indian Education: [http://content inflibnet.ac.in](http://content.inflibnet.ac.in)
- [10] <https://www.unprme.org/about>
- [11] Chakraborty T, Chatterjee B, Mishra N, Tripathi M (2020). Psychological wellbeing and Grit among Management Graduates in India: Understanding the Moderating role of Knowledge of Strength. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(06), ISSN: 1475-7192.
- [12] Conference Proceedings: Indian B- schools Leadership Conclave 2021, jointly organized by AACSB and EPSI- “Indian B- Schools: Navigating a Sustainable Future by Merging Local & Global Best Practices”, 27- 28 April 2021.
- [13] Mishra N. (2020). The Changing B School Pedagogy for the Changing Workplace”, Role of National Education Policy - 2020 in Transforming Higher Education. Eureka Publication. ISBN: 978-81-951936-5-3.
- [14] Aithal P S & Aithal S (2020) . Implementation Strategies of Higher Education Part of National Education Policy 2020 of India towards Achieving its Objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology and Social Sciences(IJMTS) , 5 (2), 283-325. ISSN: 2581-6012*
- [15] Ghonge M, Bag R, Singh A (2020) , Indian Education : Ancient, Medieval and Modern, intechopen ,published 27 Oct 2020
- [16] Kushnam P. N (2022) National Education Policy 2020: A prudent vision of India’s Soft Power in the Emerging World Over, volume 78, Issue 2, journals.sagepub.com. [https://doi.org 10 .1177/09749284221090720](https://doi.org/10.1177/09749284221090720)
- [17] Gupta A. Critical Analysis of NPE-1986 and NEP 2020 (2022). *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR) ISSN 2319-7064, 148-153*
- [18] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2019). Analysis of higher education in Indian National education policy proposal 2019 and its implementation challenges. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML), 3(2), 1-35.*
- [19] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020). Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards achieving its objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 5(2), 19-41.*
- [20] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2020). Implementation strategies of higher education part of national education policy 2020 of India towards achieving its objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS), 5(2), 283-325.*
- [21] Singh, J. D. (2011). Higher education in India–Issues, challenges and suggestions. *Higher education, 1(1), 93-103.*

- [22] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC analysis to an institution of higher education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 231-247. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [23] Ho, J. K. K. (2014). Formulation of a systemic PEST/PESTEL analysis for strategic analysis. *European academic research*, 2(5), 6478-6492. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [24] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). A new ABCD technique to analyze business models & concepts. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(4), 409-423. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [25] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Study on ABCD analysis technique for business models, business strategies, operating concepts & business systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 95-115. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [26] Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD Analysis as Research Methodology in Company Case Studies. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 2(2), 40-54. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [27] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Application of ABCD Analysis Model for Black Ocean Strategy. *International journal of applied research*, 1(10), 331-337. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [28] Aithal, A., & Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD analysis of task shifting—an optimum alternative solution to professional healthcare personnel shortage. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)*, 1(2), 36-51. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [29] Aithal, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). ABCD analysis of Dye-doped Polymers for Photonic Applications. *IRA-International Journal of Applied Sciences*, 4(3), 358-378. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [30] Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2018). Generating Wealth at the Base of the Pyramid—a Study Using ABCD Analysis Technique. *International Journal of Computational Research and Development (IJCRD)*, 3(1), 68-76. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [31] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). The study of new national institutional ranking system using ABCD framework. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(1), 389-402. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [32] Shenoy, V., & Aithal, P. S. (2016). ABCD Analysis of On-line Campus Placement Model. *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 5(2), 227-244. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [33] Kumari, P., & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Growth & Fate Analysis of Mangalore International Airport—A Case Study. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 4(2), 71-85. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [34] Aithal, P. S., & Pai T, V. (2016). Concept of Ideal Software and its Realization Scenarios. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME)*, 1(1), 826-837. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [35] Bhuvana, R., & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Blockchain based service: A case study on IBM blockchain services & hyperledger fabric. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 4(1), 94-102. [Google Scholar↗](#)

- [36] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India. *International journal of management sciences and business research*, 5(4), 159-170. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [37] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 6(1), 11-24. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [38] Aithal, P. S. (2021). Analysis of systems & technology using ABCD framework. *Chapter*, 8(1), 345-385. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [39] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 6(1), 30-44. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [40] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S., (2023). The Changing Role of Higher Education in the Era of AI-based GPTs. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 7(2), 183-197. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [41] Aithal, P. S., Kumar, P. M., & Shailashree, V. (2016). Factors & elemental analysis of six thinking hats technique using abcd framework. *International Journal of Advanced Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJATET)*, 1(1), 85-95. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [42] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2018). Factor & Elemental Analysis of Nanotechnology as GreenTechnology using ABCD Framework. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 3(2), 57-72. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [43] Aithal, P. S., & Aithal, S. (2017). Factor Analysis based on ABCD Framework on Recently Announced New Research Indices. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 1(1), 82-94. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [44] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). CCE Approach through ABCD Analysis of ‘Theory A’ on Organizational Performance. *International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME)*, 1(2), 169-185. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [45] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India. *International journal of management sciences and business research*, 5(4), 159-170. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [46] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2016). Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 6(1), 30-44. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [47] Shenoy, V., & Aithal, P. S. (2017). Quantitative ABCD Analysis of IEDRA Model of Placement Determination. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)*, 1(2), 103-113. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [48] Mendon, S., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Organic Food Product and its Impact on Purchase Intention. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 7(1), 254-278. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [49] Kumari, P., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Stress Coping Mechanisms: A Quantitative ABCD Analysis. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(2), 268-291. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [50] Prabhu, N., & Aithal, P. S. (2023). Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Green Banking Practices and its Impact on Using Green Banking Products. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 7(1), 28-66. [Google Scholar↗](#)

- [51] Raj, K., & Aithal, P. S. (2022). Assessing the Attractiveness & Feasibility of doing Business in the BoP Market–A Mixed Method Approach using ABCD Analysis Technique. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(2), 117-145. [Google Scholar](#)[↗]
- [52] Frederick, D. P., & Salins, M. (2022). Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Online Shopping. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 6(1), 313-329. [Google Scholar](#)[↗]
- [53] Nayak, P., & Kayarkatte, N. (2022). Education for Corporate Sustainability Disclosures by Higher Educational Institutions–A Quantitative ABCD Analysis. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 7(1), 465-483. [Google Scholar](#)[↗]
- [54] Nandini Prabhu, G., (2023). Quantitative ABCD Analysis of Integrating Corporate Social Responsibilities with Green Banking Practices by Banks from Customers' Attraction and Retention Perspectives in Selected Indian Banks. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 7(2), 1-37. [Google Scholar](#)[↗]

CHAPTER 3

MODERN MULTIDISCIPLINARY EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION:

The National Education Policy, also known as New Education Policy, or NEP 2020, that was released by the Ministry of Human Resources is encouraging, as it sets the dawn for wide spread of outcome-based education. To address and close the major gaps in the current educational system, NEP 2020 was created. The NEP refers to the necessity of industry institute partnerships and entrepreneurial education at various academic levels. In particular, the curriculum's learning outcomes of knowledge, skills, self-confidence, and entrepreneurial endeavours are highlighted by the NEP, which also places a strong emphasis on research, innovation, entrepreneurship, and professional education.

The NEP was released following lengthy discussions and a thorough procedure. The prior 1986 policy has been replaced with the new one. Generally speaking, we were known as the children of Lord Macaulay's and had inherited the British Colonial tradition in learning and teaching. In this paradigm, HEI must reshape the educational ecosystem by enhancing student learning, emphasising employable skills, and offering possibilities for outstanding research. There will

inevitably be a fee rise to include the highly requested components. Only Rs 11,524 is the monthly per capita income in India, which is insufficient for any household to be able to afford the country's escalating costs for higher education. Between 1989 and 2018, earnings climbed by 0.3%, but the expense of schooling increased eight times more quickly. The government can significantly influence this by lowering barriers to higher education, which will help people develop their skills.

If we look at the proposal from 2019, we discover that there was a strategy for gradually integrating employability training and vocational education into regular schooling. Nowadays, having skills is expected; it is no more a trendy concept. A policy supported by a skill-development project is being pushed for to improve employability. According to the 2019 skill report, only 4.69% of the workforce in India is skilled, while 45.6% of graduating students are employable. In contrast, 24% of the workforce in China, 52% in the US, 68% in the UK, 80% in Japan, and 96% in South Korea are skilled workers. Due to a mismatch between skill training and employability, the percentage is low in India. The objective of this paper is to study the features of the modern education system based on outcome based education for better employability [Skill Report and NEP Document].

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

The Kothari Commission in 1966, suggested that 6 % of the national income should be spent on education. It was felt that a large investment in education is necessary for the progress and growth of the economy, (Tilak 2007). India has a long history in the field of higher education. In ancient times, the country was home to socially famous universities. But even today the GER (Gross Enrolment Ratio) is low and modern education focuses not only on improving the GER but also to provide holistic development and focus on multiple intelligence and multiple languages (Hossain & Mondal (2019). [1]).

Improvements in economic reforms and the introduction of education programs that boosted people's status quo perceptions were two major trends of the 1990s. This is due to the beginning of the relationship between higher education and employability, which promotes economic independence.

This increases per capita income in a direct proportion. A focus on total economic growth was placed alongside the development of human capital, particularly under the influence of the knowledge-based society. Along with quality, quantity was considered in order to maintain expansion because higher education cannot be a viable industry without quantifiable outcomes. Therefore, the government's main duty was to disseminate both basic, secondary, and higher education.

In 2013, Ruxandra Bejinaru did a study on the effects of digitalization on the knowledge economy in education. The main goal of the study was to clarify the fundamental ideas of the digital economy while also showing how they applied to work and educational processes. This paper's major goal was to highlight how the digital economy has affected the field of education. To attain personal development and professional skills in the digital age, one must possess digital competencies and skills. The research on the educational sector the paper was done with both the European and Romanian contexts in mind. The necessity of meeting the 2020 target is the subject under discussion and how modern multidisciplinary education is made possible through digital development. Swapnil Jain in 2019 conducted the study on the Digital media impact on new generation education. He concluded that, with the help of technology, the education system is changing a lot. New teaching methods are being used for the overall education system and the delivery of the educational programs has also been improved.

An interdisciplinary and holistic education will aid in the development of well-rounded individuals with critical 21st century capacities in the arts, humanities, languages, sciences, social sciences, and professional, technical, and vocational fields; a value system for social

engagement; soft skills, like communication, discussion, and debate; with rigorous specialisation in a chosen field or fields should be the new education policy (Mishra (2020). [2]). Bloom's Taxonomy is the foundation of the present management education system. In 1956, Dr. Benjamin Bloom developed the Bloom's Taxonomy to advance critical thinking in the classroom. In 1956, the study only recognised three domains: cognitive, affective, and psychomotor. The three elements are frequently referred to as KSAs—knowledge, skills, and attitudes. The six levels of complexity within the cognitive domain are knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. The attitudes, emotions, and feelings are the main topics of the affective domain. The five levels of the affective domain are receiving, responding, valuing, organising, and characterising. (Mishra (2020). [2]). Modern day education should be based on Bloom's Taxonomy and the pedagogy should be designed to assess all the six levels of learning.

Entrepreneurship education gives people skills, educates them to think creatively, and develops uncommon skills like creativity and problem-solving. Additionally, it expands opportunities, upholds social fairness, inspires confidence, and boosts the economy. The need is greater because employability numbers are concerning and traditional jobs are disappearing, and because huge global firms' attitudes towards academia are rapidly altering. Mishra (2020). [2]). The challenges and opportunities for continual improvement in curriculum development, design, and effective implementation in HEI is imperative. The idea of building industry-oriented effective curriculum in business management and information technology that includes both industry and research experience components is the need of the hour. The curriculum model addresses the increasing growth of both the business management and information technology disciplines, as well as the need to keep the curriculum up to date with current advancements (Aithal (2016). [3]).

Higher education is an important aspect in deciding the economy, social status, technology adoption, and healthy human behaviour in every country. Improving GER to include every person of the country in higher education offers is the obligation of the country's education department. The National Education Policy of India 2020 is working towards this goal by enacting innovative policies to improve quality, attractiveness, affordability, and supply by opening higher education to the private sector while enforcing strict quality controls in all higher education institutions. By supporting merit-based admissions, merit-based and research-based continuous performers as faculty members, merit-based proven leaders in regulating bodies, and tight quality monitoring (Aithal (2020). [4]).

This paper is aimed at addressing how modern multidisciplinary learning pedagogy is imperative for higher education and integrating the concept of multidisciplinary learning and modern learning pedagogy can address the differences in the learning style of students and improve their employability skills.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY :

Objective of this paper is to study the need of the modern multidisciplinary education and how different is modern education from traditional conventional education. The study aims at :

- (1) To explore the education structure in modern multidisciplinary education
- (2) To study the different types of learning pedagogy in modern multidisciplinary education
- (3) To assess the impact of different pedagogy on students' learning and skill development
- (4) To evaluate the perception of faculty members for modern multidisciplinary education

4. METHODOLOGY:

A cross sectional design was administered, and the survey was collected through online Google forms. Two separate forms were designed, for faculty and students respectively. Overall probabilistic sampling technique was used to collect the samples. Survey sheets were shared

with management graduates entering the industry and with faculty members in management institutions or departments of management in higher education institutions. A total of proper 100 filled-in forms for faculty respondents and another 100 filled-in forms for students were used in the study.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:

Case based learning, problem solving skills, simulation-based learning, experiential learning, role play and project – based learning are some innovative teaching pedagogies, to be implemented early in the education system to develop outcome-based education for better employability. Each of these pedagogies is discussed below in detail, according to survey results analysis and discussion.

Which of the following is considered an important pedagogy of teaching. Rank them in order of preference, with 1 being the most preferred and 5 being the least preferred.

Fig. 1: Different Pedagogies in Teaching & Learning

Case-Based Learning: Case based learning is a teaching pedagogy where management and business cases are used to explain concepts, theories and applications. Around 55 % of faculty and 50 % of students feel case-based learning is the most effective teaching and learning pedagogy. On a scale of 5, case- based learning scored 3. Case based learning emphasises on analytical ability and critical thinking. Its also helps to develop decision making and communication skills, since the case is eventually presented, discussed, and strategized. Case based learning also promotes teamwork, presentation, and practice-based behaviour. The advantage of learning theory from case study is generating a more acceptable concept ability to measure the application of a theory and evidence based valid concept (Turnbull (2021). [5]).

Experiential Learning: In experiential learning the learner experiences the concepts and the theory and develops his own way of reacting and decision making. The learner reflects and analyses the situation. Board games, role plays, negotiation games, mock parliament and many more are kind of experiential learning. The internships and live projects which is a feature of modern multidisciplinary education are again another type of experiential learning. Around 60 % of the faculty feel that experiential learning is most effective way of teaching and learning. Experiential learning is very important in present day modern education and is more application oriented. It impacts learning through long lasting disciplined learning process. Experiential learning theory was developed by Kolb (1984), provides a hands-on model for relating knowledge and experience. Experiential learning supports students with deeper knowledge promotes logic based understanding and argumentation, it endorses academic growth and improves understanding (Radovic & Hummel (2021). [6]).

Project Based Learning: Project based learning system which combines classroom teaching with project (theory with practice). These projects can be desk based (pure research) where learning takes place through data analysis and interpretation, thus promoting analytical skills, decision making, and language skills. Project based learning can also be a live project in the form of a CSR project, social project or summer project. It is particularly aimed at improving the quality of education outcome, through collaboration, integrated, and self-directed learning. Application of knowledge is highest in project-based learning and gain 60 % of faculty have ranked project-based learning also as preferred method of teaching in multidisciplinary education. A significant relation is there between project based method and collaborative learning. A study by Almulla (2020) [7] shows the PBL, techniques improve students engagement through information and knowledge sharing.

Simulation Based Learning: Simulation is a man-made illustration of an actual world to attain instructional motives through simulation. It is an extension of experiential learning. Simulation exercises allows an individual to think holistically and enhance data-based decision-making skills based on management principles. Any simulation-based exercise helps to develop agility and adaptability and promote the spirit of collaboration, cooperation, and competition. Around 50 % of the faculty respondent and 60 % of the student respondents have preferred simulation-based learning as the preferred method of learning and teaching.

Team Based Learning: Team based learning is turning out to be the finest learning technique that is gaining popularity in management education. Any kind of team projects ranging from group presentation, case study competition, event management, sports activities, CSR activities are all team based. The students can apply multiple educational concepts through various activities like, communication, teamwork, leadership roles, negotiation, decision making and critical thinking. In the study team-based learning is preferred by 60 % both of faculty and students. Team based learning improves students' grades, exam performance, and classroom performance. Team based learning allows deeper understanding and more confidence. Some students who find difficulty in free discussions or be forthcoming, perform better through team-based learning. This method moves beyond from a traditional mode of learning and provides learners with more academic learning in a practical way [8].

Fig. 2: Competencies & Skills

The effectiveness of the above-mentioned pedagogy depends upon the skills it develops in a student. These skills are required for better employability and job readiness. The different skills identified in outcome-based learning are, Problem Solving, Analytical Skills, Critical thinking, Decision Making, and Communication skills, The student respondents felt the Analytical Skill is most important of all the five skills and it scored an average of 4.5 on a scale

of 5. The next most required skill is Critical Thinking, scoring 4.3 on a scale of 5. The first two skills were followed by Decision Making (3.5 on a scale of 5), Communication skills, 3.5 on a scale of 5 and problem-solving skills, 3.2 on a scale of 5. Learning outcomes in different pedagogy are described by the abilities, knowledge, and values a student can deliver.

6. THE ROLE OF FACULTY IN OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION- A MODERN MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH:

This study will be beneficial because faculty engagement will bring more positivity and innovativeness in the Higher Education Institutions in terms of outcome-based education. What has been observed in the study is that faculty members are not individual workers, working in silos, they are integrated into a system that has students, management, institutions, and other stakeholders. Faculty engagement is required to realize higher levels of student learning attainment. What had happened earlier was the decoupling of teaching role and research role of faculty, even more because remuneration for faculty was low. So, it was not expected of faculty to accomplish both roles. But in the new career prospects under Sixth and Seventh pay commission, teaching, research, and institution building has been integrated. With increased faculty engagement, there are strategic collaborations between faculty and support professionals, thereby bringing more faculty engagement in academic institutions. The positivity of faculty engagement is transmitted to the students, thus making learning more student oriented.

A very important observation of the study was the survey of the faculty members, through whom the change in higher education is designed. What has been discussed and seen during the research interview is that the faculty have expressed the support of the senior management and academic leaders in their meaningful contribution. Teachers mentioned that they expect respectful treatment and two-way communication for better engagement and performance. Hence HODs, Principals, Directors, and Deans, along with the Management has a big role to play in the effective employee engagement. High- quality leadership, proper governance and ethical practices in academic institutions can contribute towards better employee engagement. During the in-depth interview, many faculty members mentioned that behaviour of the senior academic leaders have impact on faculty engagement. Due to increased role of technology in teaching, young faculty /teachers are adept in it and reverse mentoring is on the rise. While senior academic leaders share knowledge and research skills with young faculty members, they in turn teach the senior members technology-based learning. This has improved faculty engagement in HEIs. The analysis of the research is discussed below.

Outcome based education is a shift from content-based learning

Fig. 3: Perception of Outcome Based Education

OBE Covers Curriculum Structures and Procedures

Fig. 4: Curriculum of Outcome Based Education

OBE is student centered learning

Fig. 5: Student Centric Learning

IT Infrastructure plays a decisive role in delivering OBE

Fig. 6: Role of Infrastructure in OBE

E- Library and Library resources play an important role in OBE

Fig. 7: Role of Library in OBE

Proper Manpower Planning and training is effective in delivering OBE

Fig. 8: Manpower Planning and Training in OBE

Autonomy of teachers in teaching is important for setting goal standards in learning

Fig. 9: Autonomy of Teachers in OBE

organization provides lots of training wrt OBE

Fig. 10: Role of Training in OBE

Rewards & Recognition determines the teachers' engagement in delivering OBE

Fig. 11: Role of Rewards & Recognition in OBE

Proper Research and Research Incentives contributes towards OBE

Fig. 13: Role of Research in OBE

Commitment of teachers towards goal settings in education is important for OBE

Fig. 14: Commitment of Teachers in Goal Setting

According to survey results, 52.8 % strongly agree and 41.8 % agree that outcome-based education is a shift from content-based education. Around 51 % of the faculty respondents agree that OBE follows proper curriculum structure and procedure. OBE is student centric learning and is thereby an important feature of modern multidisciplinary learning. The respondents, strongly agree (50 %) and agree (41%) that OBE is student centric learning. Around 80 % of the respondents agree that infrastructure and technology have a big role to play in OBE, assisted by proper library and E- library facilities, as expressed by 90 % of the respondents. To make OBE more effective, autonomy of teachers, proper man- power planning and training is necessary. Which means, sufficient time and resources must be invested. Regarding research incentives, rewards, and recognition of teachers are divided in their opinion. Around, 37.7 % agree that research incentives should be there for teachers' commitment, while 24.5 % disagree that research incentives contribute towards OBE. One observation is that more than 70 % of faculty agree that commitment of teachers in goal setting is very important for OBE.

7. ANALYSIS OF MODERN MULTIDISCIPLINARY OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION USING ABCD FRAMEWORK :

In exploratory research, analysis refers to the process of examining and interpreting gathered information. Exploratory research is to gain insights, generate postulates, identify patterns or relationships, and generate new knowledge about a particular phenomenon or problem. There are many analysis frameworks used in scholarly research which include SWOC analysis framework for internal analysis [10], PESTEL analysis framework for external analysis [11], and ABCD analysis framework for stakeholder analysis [12-15]. Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages (ABCD) analysis framework is proposed in the year 2015 to analyse systems, concepts, ideas, strategies, products/services, materials, etc [12-15]. ABCD analysis framework can be used both qualitatively and quantitatively depending upon requirements [12-15]. The qualitative ABCD analysis framework consists of (1) ABCD listing from information gathering from primary and secondary sources [12-15], (2) ABCD listing from Stakeholders' point of view of a system [12-15], (3) Factor and Elemental analysis using ABCD framework [12-15]. In this section, we have used ABCD listing from stakeholders' points of view (both learners and teachers) on ancient education compared to modern education in Higher Education.

(A) Advantages:

- (1) Focuses on problem solving and experiential learning.
- (2) Is more practical and application oriented.
- (3) Is student centric and optimises teaching and learning.
- (4) The engagement process is continuous and less monotonous.

(5) Innovative teaching pedagogy is used in types of techniques.

(B) Benefits:

- (1) Development of long-term knowledge retention and ability to retain and recall learning.
- (2) Reinforces understanding of different subjects.
- (3) Use of different and diverse pedagogy, thereby promoting self-paced learning.
- (4) More participatory learning in a constructive manner.
- (5) Development of transferable skills thereby making learners more confident

(C) Constraints:

- (1) Huge cost and resources required for implementing outcome-based education.
- (2) Training of all faculty in the various modules is time consuming and expensive.
- (3) Unpreparedness of students and teachers due to unfamiliarity
- (4) Difficulty in assessing the shortfall and short coming of the different pedagogies.
- (5) Difficulty in mapping suitable pedagogy for candidates.

(D) Disadvantages:

- (1) Challenge of time management between academic and non-academic activities.
- (2) May lead to less academic orientation and poor performance in exams.
- (3) Degree of relevancy and applicability may vary depending upon candidates' calibre.
- (4) Training of faculty members across different organizations will be difficult and is a lengthy process.
- (5) Skills and competencies developed will change from time to time and has to be developed accordingly.

8. CONCLUSION:

Modern multidisciplinary outcome-based education collaborates problem-solving, curriculum aligned topics, and diverse contexts. The different approaches to learning based on real-life problems facilitate faster and better learning, with knowledge creation and knowledge transfer. Setting goals and expectations for both the learner and the trainer and highlighting the purpose of problem-based learning is of utmost importance. The existing knowledge gap is filled with a logical approach, and students are given the opportunity to present their ideas and findings. Individual learning is thereby ensured through group learning. The challenges of modern outcome-based education in terms of time, resources, and willingness of the top management, can be addressed through proper manpower planning, resource allocation, and futuristic education. If education is for the next generation it has to be outcome-based, supporting Bloom's Taxonomy. According to Blooms Taxonomy (Blooms 1965), cognitive domains involve the development of new skills. Learning creates better knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation. Outcome-based education focuses on cognitive; mental skills, i.e., knowledge, psychomotor, i.e., hard skills, and affective, i.e., attitude building. After any learning episode, the learner will acquire new skills, knowledge, or attitude.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Hossain A & Mondal G. C. (2019). History and Milestone of Higher Education in India, *International Journal of research an Analytical Review*, 6(1), 978-983. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [2] Mishra N. (2020). The Changing B School Pedagogy for the Changing Workplace. Role of National Education Policy - 2020 in Transforming Higher Education. Eureka Publication. ISBN: 978-81-951936-5-3.
- [3] Aithal, P. S. (2016) Student Centric Curriculum design and Implementation- Challenges & Opportunities in Business Management & IT Education, *IRA International Journal of Education and Multidisciplinary Studies*, 4(3), 423-437. [Google Scholar↗](#)

- [4] Aithal, P. S. (2020) Analysis of the Indian National Education Policy 2020 towards Achieving its Objectives. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 19-41. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [5] Turnbull, D., Chugh, R., Luck, Jo. (2021). The use of case study design in learning management systems research: A label of convenience. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 20(1), 01-11. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [6] Radovic, S., Hummel Hans, G. K. & Vermenlen, M. (2021). The Challenge of designing more experiential learning in higher education programs in the field of teacher education: A systematic review study. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 40(5-6), 545-560. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [7] Almulla, M. A. (2020). The Effectiveness of the Project Based Learning: PBL Approach as a way to Engage Students in Learning, *Sage Open*, 10(3), 01-09. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [8] Swanson, E., McCulley, L., Solis, M. (2017). The effect of team based learning on content knowledge: A meta analysis, *Active learning in higher education*, 20(1), 39-50. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [9] Tilak, J. B. G. (2007). Post-elementary education, poverty, and development in India. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 27(1), 435-445. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [10] Aithal, P. S., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Applying SWOC analysis to an institution of higher education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(7), 231-247. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [11] Ho, J. K. K. (2014). Formulation of a systemic PEST/PESTEL analysis for strategic analysis. *European academic research*, 2(5), 6478-6492. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [12] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V. T., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). A new ABCD technique to analyze business models & concepts. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 5(4), 409-423. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [13] Aithal, P. S. (2016). Study on ABCD analysis technique for business models, business strategies, operating concepts & business systems. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 4(1), 95-115. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [14] Aithal, P. S., Shailashree, V., & Kumar, P. M. (2015). Application of ABCD Analysis Model for Black Ocean Strategy. *International journal of applied research*, 1(10), 331-337. [Google Scholar↗](#)
- [15] Aithal, A., & Aithal, P. S. (2017). ABCD analysis of task shifting—an optimum alternative solution to professional healthcare personnel shortage. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Pharmacy (IJHSP)*, 1(2), 36-51. [Google Scholar↗](#)

CHAPTER 4

ROLE OF EXTRA CURRICULAR ACTIVITIES IN OUTCOME BASED EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION:

Modern day economy is fast changing with various factors interplaying and interchanging. Technological advancements, disintegrated markets, versatile competition, massive shifts in socio-economic and socio-political environment coupled with natural disasters and man-made disasters. These challenging situations in business demand actions with high speed, resilience, and multidisciplinary approach. These changes will be brought by the workforce and the manpower engaged. Hence it is imperative that the manpower is skilled in handling the volatile, uncertain, complex, and ambiguous (VUCA) environment. Surviving and thriving in a rapidly changing external environment requires mental flexibility, analytical ability, creativity, self-learning, self-awareness and most importantly risk taking. All this is possible only through extracurricular and co-curricular activities for learners in high education.

VUCA education should embrace change, where learners should direct their own course of learning through extracurricular activities. VUCA thinking involves developing the ability to anticipate and adapt to changes quickly, Learners should be trained to think beyond the boundaries and take decisions independently. [1 & 2]

Extracurricular activities are the range of activities planned along with regular curriculum to meet learners' interest and aptitude. These activities help the learners to be more involved and engaged in their own groups and development social and soft skills to promote wellbeing. These activities can include events, voluntary work, sports, and leadership roles in different committees.

Behaviour disorders and discipline among students can be improved through curricular and co-curricular activities. Studies conducted by Eccles and Gootman (2002) [3] reveal that extracurricular activities have positive impact on learners' overall development. A study by Whitney et al (2012) [4] highlights essential elements of wellbeing in grooming adults. Amongst the other parameters mentioned in the study, ability to generate new information and use of social indicators is essential for development of individual.

Holland and Andre (1987) [5] mentioned five areas of extracurricular activities, personal and social characteristics, academic achievements, educational aspirations and attainments, participants roles in activities and environmental social context for development of individuals. All these are possible only through curricular and co-curricular activities along with academic rigour. The study showed that participation in these activities is highly correlated with higher levels of self-esteem, involvement in social activities with better academic grades, feeling of control over ones' own life, and lower undesired activities.

Fredricks & Eccles (2006) [6], in their research on effect of extracurricular participation on beneficial outcomes, suggests a positive effect on academic, psychological and behavioural outcomes.

Co-curricular activities take place beyond the classroom and sometimes outside the boundaries of classroom, outside the structure of just academic learning. Co-curricular activities complement academic learning.

The role of extracurricular activities in education date back to the 1930s. Earlier modes of education focused more on academic learnings and output. We see today there is more emphasis on extracurricular and co-curricular activities like events, live projects, internships, participation in collegiate activities, sports, and competitions.

2. OBJECTIVES:

1. To assess the role of different extracurricular and co-curricular activities in higher education.
2. To evaluate the role of extracurricular and co-curricular activities in student empowerment.
3. To suggest strategies for effective implementation of extracurricular activities in higher education

3. METHODOLOGY:

The study is exploratory and qualitative in nature. Data is obtained through survey method to study the impact of extracurricular activities. The paper is based on analysis of selected relevant papers and articles related to extracurricular activities. The authors have attempted to incorporate the analysis of primary data to establish the role of extracurricular and co-curricular activities. One part of the analysis is based on the data of 100 complete responses received from postgraduate students in Management Education in Mumbai.

4. DISCUSSION:

- 1. To assess the role of extracurricular and co-curricular activities in higher education.**

The skills required for the VUCA world is more than just reading, writing and numerical. There is more emphasis on critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication. The skills required by the 21st century manager cannot be developed in a traditional classroom setting. Students need to be actively engaged in their learning and have opportunities to apply what they have learnt. The main skills identified are creativity, emotional intelligence, communication, leadership, technology application, critical thinking, problem solving, collaboration, information literacy, social skills, media literacy, productivity, project management, decision making, adaptability, flexibility, ethics, life skills, analytical ability and cross-cultural skills. We can categorise the skills into (1) Learning Skills – Critical Thinking, Creativity, Collaboration and communication; (2) Literacy Skills- Information, Media and Technology; (3) Life Skills- Flexibility, Leadership, Initiative, Productivity, Social Skills.

Some engaging co- curricular activities are internships, live projects, presentations, role-plays, management by movies and book reviews. These activities can form a part or can be a complete course in the assessment of credit courses in curriculum. The co-curricular activity through its approach addresses the most important skills required by the 21st century manager.[7]

Table 1- Mapping Activity with Skills

ACTIVITY TYPE	COMPONENTS	SKILLS DEVELOPED
Co -Curricular Activity	Internships, Live Projects, Presentations, Role Play, Management by Movies, Book Reviews, Immersion Programs and Value- Add Activities	Learning Skills – critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and communication Literacy Skills- Information, Media and Technology Emotional Intelligence, Decision Making, Analytical Ability, Ethics, Cross Cultural Skills, Problem Solving
ACTIVITY TYPE	COMPONENTS	SKILLS DEVELOPED
Extra- Curricular Activity	Cultural Events, Forum Events, Sports Events, Competitions, Street Plays, CSR Activities, Literary Fests, College Club Activities, Rural Immersion, Participation in Exhibitions, Outbound Activities and many more	Life Skills- Flexibility, Leadership, Initiative, Productivity, Social Skills. Collaboration, Creativity, Cross Cultural Skills, Problem Solving, Project Management, Ethics, Adaptability and Communication

While the co- curricular activities focus on learning skills and literacy skills, the extracurricular activities help to develop the intangible elements of a student’s everyday life. Critical thinking is all about finding solutions to problems and creativity deals with finding fresh approach and thinking out of box. But problem solving and creativity will be functional only when communication is lucid and ability to work and collaborate with others is mastered. Collaboration in the VUCA world is of utmost importance and communication is the glue that can bring all the skills together. Information skills, literacy skills and technology skills help students understand facts, data points and application of the data to solve problem and in making decisions. These skills can only be developed through extracurricular and cocurricular activities. However, the learning skills and literacy skills alone will not help anyone adapt to the changing circumstances. It’s the life skills, i.e. FLIPS (flexibility, leadership, initiative, productivity and social skills) which can help achieving the individual goals and the organizational goals

2. To evaluate the role of extracurricular and co- curricular activities in student empowerment

The most powerful approach of empowering students is done by encouraging them to think diversely, dream big in life, express their opinions freely and be engaged in learning in a more democratic and participative way. In this study, questionnaire comprising all aspects of extracurricular and cocurricular activities were circulated amongst 130 students of which 100 responses, which were complete in all aspects were considered for analysis.

Table – II Evaluating Co- Curricular and Extra Curricular Activities

Question	Opinion (%)
What contributes more to your learning Academic or Non- Academic events	Academic events- 34 Non- Academic- 66
Should education be Multidisciplinary or Specialization Oriented	Multidisciplinary- 60 Specialization Oriented- 40
Do your internship training support in your Final Placements	Extremely Helpful- 35 Helpful to a Large Extent- 65
How have Live Projects have contributed to learning and Placements	Extremely Helpful- 60 Helpful to a Large Extent- 40
How have the extracurricular activities contributed towards Leadership Development	To a Great Extent- 70 To Some Extent- 30
How have the extracurricular activities contributed towards Decision Making Skills	To a Great Extent- 50 To Some Extent- 50
How have the extracurricular activities contributed towards Problem Solving Skills	To a Great Extent- 50 To Some Extent- 50
How have all the extracurricular and co- curricular activities contributed towards overall personality development	To a Great Extent- 14 To Some Extent- 86

The result of the analysis is mixed, learners agree that non-academic activities, in the form of extra-curricular activities is most desirable, however it cannot be done at the cot of academic activities. The challenge is in incorporating non- academic activities in the form of extracurricular activities along with the curriculum. Learners have expressed that multidisciplinary education is more preferred than only specialization-based education, this is why most management institutes and higher education institutes have introduced the concept of major and minor and electives. The impact of extracurricular activities in overall development of individuals, will always depend on the institutions approach, endeavour, and commitment towards overall personality development for skills required in the VUCA world. To improve the opinion of respondents towards the impact of extracurricular activities on overall development, higher education institutes will have to design outcome-based activities and map these activities with curriculum and co- curriculum designs.

3. To suggest strategies for effective implementation of extracurricular activities in higher education

Extracurricular activities are sources that have long been a part of the educational system; students participate in these types of activities, which do not fall under the purview of standard curriculum and teaching methods. Students of all ages and standards participate in these activities at all levels. Sports, gaming, art, music, theatre, poetry, student newspaper, clubs, and government are examples of extracurricular activities. Participation in all these activities, or just one of them, has been linked to social and academic curriculum. There are various perspectives on what constitutes an extracurricular activity. Outside-of-institute activities may include dances, team sports, and performing arts, whilst inside-of-institute involvement activities may include within the group and academic groups. Different levels of activity involvement and participation may have a positive impact on future success for those who participate; individuals who give their all to extracurricular activities achieve success and sometimes even choose that activity as a career or profession. The primary goal of this research article is to explore how extracurricular activities might influence academic growth, social skills, and the development of a talent or ability inside oneself. There are various perspectives on what constitutes an extracurricular activity. Some strategies suggested for effective implementation of extracurricular and co- curricular activities are, [8- 11, 13]

(1) using positive reinforcement activities, students like to hear their own voice and resounding success, making every event a fun experience can allow more meaningful learning,

(2) permitting creative expressions, students should be allowed not just to say what they think, but also to say it in whichever way they want. Allow learners to be creative with the how, and one will probably be delighted with the what. This can be accomplished by organising debates, competitions, and so forth.

(3) providing more discussion time for students, so that they can explore and develop better ideas, many are concerned that dedicating too much time to debate, we will not allow time to cover the content that has to be covered. The reality is that both debate and having an opinion on a topic improves learning and memory.

(4) Another very important strategy to implement extracurricular activities is through different specialization wise forums and events. The concepts are easily learnt along with other literacy skills and life skills.

(5) The internal components of assessments of different courses, can be designed through projects, presentations, and models.

(6) Using the concept of 70: 20: 10 model of learning, the curriculum and teaching modules can be designed. In any higher education learning and in professional courses, 70 % of the learning takes place through experiments, experiences, and assignments. Around 20 % of learning is through developmental relationships and only 10 % is through actual course work and academics. In fact, the basics of learning skills, literacy skills and life skills are fulfilled through the concept of 70: 20: 10 learning model.

5. CONCLUSION:

Results of the study shows that extracurricular and co- curricular activities improve the academic and social activities. Students participating in extracurricular activities have better experiential learning. Participation in extracurricular activities help in character development and social skill development. Apart from developing communication skills and team spirits,

students learn task-oriented roles and relationship-oriented roles. While these activities promote team cohesiveness and collaboration and make the students independent and confident. Well-structured engaging extracurricular activities are effective in developing holistic individual with industry readiness. [12]

Higher Education Institutions must equip students with Life Skills, Emotional Intelligence and Values that will stand them in good stead for the future. This can be made possible by the skilled faculty, who can empower each student to excel academically, emotionally, socially, and spiritually. Fortified by a holistic curriculum and backed by a modern teaching process, the students can come forth into the world as responsible, learned, confident, considerate, and sentient global citizens.

Academic leaders must aim to educate students with a multitude disciplined learning experience, for their holistic (physical, intellectual, emotional, social & spiritual) development. They must encourage students in the pursuit of brilliance, to emerge as confident and responsible leaders dedicated to serving the society with benevolence.

REFERENCES:

1. <http://hbr.org>. What VUCA Really Means For You, “ Accessed on 11/7/2023
2. [http:// www. VUCA- World .Org](http://www.VUCA-World.Org). Accessed on 11/7/2023
3. Eccles J & Gootman J (2002) Community Programs to Promote Youth Development – ERIC, National Academy Press, ISBN-0-309-07275-1, <http://www.nap.edu>
4. Whitney E, Moore G & Hansen D (2012) , Construct – Validity of the Engagement with Challenge Measure for Adolescent Structural and Criterion – Validity Evidence, Psychology, Vol 3, No.10
5. Holland. A & Andre T (1987) , Participation in extracurricular activities in secondary schools. What is Known, What needs to be Known ? Review of Educational Research 57 (4), 437-466, <http://doi.org>, 10.2307/1170431
6. Fredricks J A & Eccles J S (2006) , Is extracurricular participation associated with beneficial outcomes? Concurrent and longitudinal relations. Developmental Psychology, 42 (4), 698-713, [https:// doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649, 42.4.698](https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.42.4.698)
7. Applied Education System, What are the 21st Century Skills (2022) <http://www.aeseducation.com>. Accessed on 16/7/2023
8. Ravi M.N & Shetty S (2020), Extracurricular Activity – A Tool Beyond Curriculum for Student Empowerment, Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovation Research (JETIR), [www, jetiir.org](http://www.jetiir.org), ISSN 2349-5162, Vol 7, Issue 12

9. Buckely P & Lee Paul (2021), Active Learning in Higher Education, Vol 22 (1), 37-48, Sage Pub.com journals. DOI 10.1177/14697874/8808988
10. Munir S & Zaheer M (2021), The role of extracurricular activities in increasing student engagement, www, emerald.com/insight/2414-6994.htm. DOI 10.1108/AAOUJ-08-2021-0080
11. Ileriturk D (2023) Evaluation of extracurricular activities in education according to pre-school teacher candidates' views, Social sciences & Humanities, Open 8 , 100524, Elsevier, DOI.org /10.1016/j .ssaho.2023.100524
12. Christison C (2013), The Benefits of Participating in Extracurricular Activities, BU Journal of Graduate Studies in Education, Vol 5, Issue 2, Accessed on 9 /7/2023
13. Balyer A & Gunduz Y (2012) Effects of Structured extracurricular facilities on students' academic and social development, Procedia- Social and Behavioural science 46, 4803-4807, DOI,org/10/1016/j.sbsro.2012.06.338 , SciVerse Science Direct, Elsevier.

CHAPTER 4

IMPORTANCE OF MENTAL HEALTH IN HIGHER EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability is often defined as meeting the present's needs without compromising the future generation's ability to meet their own needs (Brundtland, 1987). This definition highlights the spiritual dimension of sustainability, as it requires balancing the interests of present and future generations. Mental wellbeing refers to an individual's beliefs and values, often related to a

higher power or a sense of purpose. Mental wellbeing and sustainability are two distinct but related concepts. Research has shown a positive relationship between an individual's mental wellbeing orientation and support for sustainable practices. For example, Dhiman (2016) argued that the preservation of the inviolability of the planet is only possible if the individual's life is based on moral and spiritual awareness. Further, "there is no sustainability without wellbeing. On similar lines, Marques (2016) established a link between moral principles and sustainability. To achieve sustainability, there is a need to maximise the triple bottom line (TBL) through fair and beneficial practices towards people (community), the environment (natural capital), and profitability (economic value) (Elkington, 2004 & 1998).

TBL is an approach to measure the three bottom lines, namely, people, planet, and profit, which are affected by business operations. 'People', the dimension of TBL, consists of all the people directly or indirectly impacted by the business operations, including employees, suppliers, and the community. It highlights that everyone's well-being is considered (Elkington & Rowlands, 1999), i.e., business leaders must fulfil their responsibility towards society. Researchers have defined well-being as a state of mind that includes feeling good and functioning well, developing a sense of happiness or contentment, realising one's potential, having a purpose, and establishing positive relationships. Ruggeri et al. (2020) explained it as "a sustainable condition that allows the individual or population to develop and thrive." Aksoy and Bayram (2020) empirically established that sustainable happiness is achieved through sustainable development. The purpose of sustainable development is to improve the quality of life of people. In this context, the authors discovered that the environmental and social dimension of the triple bottom line influences sustainable happiness. Several pieces of evidence in the literature exemplify that sustainability aims to improve wellbeing (Helne & Hirvilammi, 2015; Bakar et al., 2015; McGregor, 2014). The importance of well-being has been widely acknowledged (Facchinetti & Siletti, 2021). Scholars contended that policymakers should focus on well-being (Diener & Seligman, 2004). John Carroll, in his book "Sustainability and Spirituality", argued that models of real sustainability should correlate to people who put their faith in values, i.e., people who have developed deep spirituality. Many others scholars have established a connection between wellbeing and sustainability such that sustainability requires ethical commitment and values to facilitate the essential shift in consciousness that a sustainable mind set requires

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. To understand the role of mental wellbeing in sustainability
2. To explore the factors that contribute to overall mental wellbeing
3. To suggest a framework for higher education to implement and integrate mental wellbeing programs in regular activities.

3. METHODOLOGY:

The Warwick- Edinburgh Mental Wellbeing Scale (WEMWBS) was adapted and used for the study. The WEMWBS was developed by an expert panel drawing on academic literature, qualitative research with focus group and psychometric testing of the existing scale (Tennant, R, et al 2007) . The scale was adapted to understand the mental wellbeing of students in higher education. The data was collected from 230 students spread across five different groups. Participants were asked to complete the questionnaire and discuss the concepts of mental wellbeing during the focus group. The discussions from the focus group were used in suggesting the framework for mental wellness in higher education. The questionnaire had 14 items, covering broader attributes like, self-esteem, confidence, optimism, and problem solving. The questions covered aspects of complete wellbeing like positive attitude, positive functioning, competence, autonomy, clear thinking, self-acceptance, positive energy, and outlook towards personal development. Participants were required to tick the box that best describes them, using 5 point Likert Scale (always-5, often-4, sometimes- 3, rarely-2 and never-1). The Likert Scale represents a score for each item from 5 to 1 respectively, giving a maximum score of 70 and minimum score of 14. The overall score of the respondents were calculated by totalling the scores for each item and equal weights.

In this study the researchers conducted factor analysis on 14 items, grouping them into three of four each and one group of two, based on commonalities. This method helped the interpretability of the results. Results reveal distinct themes, within each group, contributing valuable insights for suggesting a framework for implementing mental well-being strategies in higher education.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

The summary of the responses for the 14 items in the questionnaire was analysed. While it is desirable that the results should be more towards Always, the results are more inclined towards Sometime and Often. There are few cases of rarely and never and these are the matters of concern for an organization. Activities should be designed to address these issues.

Table – 1 Summary of Responses of Mental Well-being

	Items	Always (%)	Often (%)	Sometime (%)	Rarely (%)	Never (%)
1	I am very optimistic about the future	41	35.8	21	1.7	0.5
2	I feel very useful	26.2	41	29.7	2.7	0.4
3	I feel very relaxed	7.9	23.1	41	24.5	3.5
4	I take interest in other people	21	10.5	54.6	10.5	3.5

5	I have energy to spare for other activities	13.5	33.2	38.9	12.2	2.2
6	I have been dealing with problems well	15.7	39.2	36.7	7.4	0.9
7	I have been thinking clearly	20.5	41.5	30.6	6.1	1.3
8	I have been feeling good about myself	28.5	39	28.5	6.6	1.8
9	I feel close to other people	12.7	29.3	38.4	16.6	3
10	I have been feeling confident	22.3	40.6	31.9	3.9	1.3
11	I can make up my mind about many things	17	38.9	34.9	9.2	0
12	I am always loved	23.1	35.8	29.7	10.5	0.9
13	I am interested in New Things	48.2	35.8	14.2	1.8	0
14	I always feel cheerful	27.1	38.4	28.6	7	0.9

Table- II Summary of Factors contributing to Mental Wellbeing

	FACTORS	AVERAGE
1	I am very optimistic about the future	4.1
2	I feel very useful	3.8
3	I feel very relaxed	3.1
4	I take interest in other people	3.3
5	I have energy to spare for other activities	3.4
6	I have been dealing with problems well	3.6
7	I have been thinking clearly	3.7
8	I have been feeling good about myself	3.8
9	I feel close to other people	3.3
10	I have been feeling confident	3.7
11	I can make up my mind about many things	3.6
12	I am always loved	3.6
13	I am interested in New Things	4.3
14	I always feel cheerful	3.8

The respondents are positive and optimistic about the future, are cheerful and are feeling good about themselves. These could be due to the previous few weeks 'activities in the Institute, which increased their positivity and outlook towards life. During the focus group the respondents were asked to describe the previous few weeks' activities

The rationale behind grouping the 14 factors into three groups of four and one group of two was based on the constructs of the four broader factors of mental wellbeing.

Self-esteem : self-esteem is the determination or thought we hold about ourselves. It's the capacity to which we sense ourselves to be valuable and capable human beings. There are six factors influencing self-esteem:

1. **Family environment:** Each varies in its social and economic condition with different backgrounds.
2. **Achievement:** Academic achievement and goals related to their hobbies play a crucial role in forming a positive, healthy view of the self.
3. **Physical appearance:** Physical appearance such as hair, figure, height, weight, skin colour may also influence the self-esteem of an individual.
4. **Self-belief:** A person who has a high confidence level may learn things quickly, trust that they can complete tasks to a good standard and this subsequently may boost their self-esteem.
5. **Feedback from friends and others:** Positive and negative note and feedback from friends and others may encourage or break an individual's self-esteem.

Item 3, 8, 12 and 14 from the questionnaire were considered under self esteem

Self-esteem

I feel very relaxed	3.07
I have been feeling good about myself	3.8
I am always loved	3.6
I always feel cheerful	3.8
	3.5675

Confidence:

Confidence comes from feelings of well-being, acceptance of self (body and mind) and self-esteem. It is the belief in individuals own ability, skills, and experience. Positive thinking, practice, training, knowledge and talking to other people are all useful ways to help improve or boost your confidence levels. Item - 2, 4, 9 and 10 were considered under confidence. Confidence is an outcome of self esteem and is tested from the score of both the factors of mental wellbeing.

I always feel cheerful	3.8
I take interest in other people	3.3
I feel close to other people	3.3
I have been feeling confident	3.7
	3.525

Problem Solving: Research shows that the development of a variety of thinking modes and abilities, such as algorithmic thinking, cooperativity, creativity, critical thinking, personal tenacity, prospecting, perspective-taking, and empathic concern contributes towards problem solving skills. Item 5, 6, 7 and 11 were considered under problem solving skills,

I have energy to spare for other activities	3.4
I have been dealing with problems well	3.6
I have been thinking clearly	3.7
I am able to make up my mind about many things	3.7
	3.6

Optimism: There are mainly three components of optimism. The perspective involves the use of opportunity “sensing”, positive mood, and resilience. To a much greater extent than pessimists, optimists address change by identifying potential benefits. Item number 1 and 13 in the questionnaire were considered for optimism.

I am very optimistic about the future	4.15
I am interested in New Things	4.3
	4.225

Framework for Student Wellbeing in Higher Education Institutions

National crime data for 2022 is grim reading. Among the grimmest statistics is that the national daily average of suicides was nearly 500. What does this say? Chronic levels of stress remain unaddressed. The three big gaps are poor mental health infrastructure, grey areas in relevant laws, and taboos that stop people from seeking help.

In 2022, a third of all who died by suicide were farmers, daily wagers. And Over 13,000 students form the other large group committing suicides. Mental health experts say ‘suicide clusters’, such as in Kota, need niche tactics with continuous psychiatric evaluation and care. Yet in Kota, where 23 youngsters have died by suicide in 2022-23, authorities opted to put springs in ceiling fans, and nets below balconies. How is that a solution?

Survivors need support, long-term help. Where do they go when home circumstances push them to the brink? After all, the data says cause for 32% suicide cases was “family problems”. Residences can be unsafe places, for both men and women. Prior attempts are a predictor for more attempts. Who does the surveillance? Indians fall back on family-community support for most needs – financial to personal, yet a mental health issue is a no-go area. Addressing the taboo on mental distress is a task beyond the capacity of India’s network of suicide helplines and support networks – still largely privately run, by psychiatrists and NGOs. Government networks, where they exist, are often inaccessible and understaffed.

Nearly 35% of suicide deaths were in the 18-30 age group. That’s part of the demographic dividend pushed to the edge. [<https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/toi-editorials/chronicles-of-death-suicide-is-a-rising-trend-in-india-including-among-the-young/.6 December 2023>]

Majority of the youths spend a substantial amount of time in the Institutes, with their peers, faculty members and friends. It is therefore imperative that every institution should have proper mental health cell, to discuss, counsel and prevent mental health problems amongst youngsters.

Research indicates that student mental wellbeing is supported when curriculum and teaching practices foster students’ intrinsic interests and communicate the importance and value of the knowledge and skills being developed. Student mental wellbeing is also supported when curriculum design and learning experiences build students’ self-efficacy, problem solving skills, teamwork, flexibility in approach, and create social connections – among students, and between students and academic teachers. Engaging curriculum and learning experiences help

educators understand the needs of diverse students and adopt teaching practices that best support their learning. Diverse students have diverse learning requirements, higher education institutions should allow flexibility to the students for holistic development and mental well-being.

Activities suggested for students in the Institutes.

1. Providing cohesive, engaging extra-curricular activities that foster a sense of belonging for students from diverse backgrounds.
- 2 Auditing and enhancing physical spaces to ensure access to appropriate spaces for private study, social interaction, and relaxation activities.
- 3 Building partnerships with student societies and student groups to prevent risk of isolation or discrimination – e.g. indigenous students; students with disabilities; international students; LGBTIQ students; and ‘mature age’ students.
4. Auditing and enhancing student facilities to ensure access to: healthy food options and food preparation equipment.
5. Sports facilities and events to unleash hidden talents and encourage other activities apart from academics.
6. Engaging students in the co-creation of a ‘code of conduct’ on respectful communications and appropriate use of information and communication technologies in a learning environment. This is possible through student committees and clubs.
7. Having seminars and lectures that promote inclusion and diversity and create awareness about such policies and processes in the Institute
8. Ensuring all students are aware of policies to address discrimination, bullying and harassment and of complaint processes for redressing offensive, intimidating or discriminatory behaviour

Need for Leadership at Higher Education Institutions

There is need of a high-profile leadership and advocacy in the HEIs. The responsibility for student mental health and wellbeing should be explicitly mentioned within senior academic. The academic leaders should monitor and evaluate the implementation of mental wellbeing strategies in the Institution.

1. Distributed model of responsibility for student wellbeing in all faculties and student services
2. Identifying faculty and staff with responsibilities for student wellbeing
3. Fostering partnerships with mental health professionals and other health service providers in the university and the local community.
4. Active student involvement in the co-creation of policies, programs and activities related to student mental health.
5. Student-led activities and events to promote mental health and wellbeing.
6. Mental health training programs to support student leaders.
7. Financial support to student organisations and groups to encourage and support to run activities and events to promote student mental health and wellbeing

8. To assess the examination policies, anti-ragging policies and procedures, placement support and mentoring programs in the institute

Possible indicators of progress for institutional self-monitoring:

#	INDICATORS
1	Proportion of programs that offer flexible course loads and progression Freedom of choice for specialization and electives.
2	Student feedback on how their mental health status.
3	Proportion of students who report having had a positive experience working with their peers to complete learning tasks
4	Proportion of students who report a sense of social connection with students and faculty in their course (e.g. having made at least one or two friends within their cohort; being confident a staff member knows their name)
5	Student feedback on surveys on the extent to which subjects/courses stimulated their interest
6	Student feedback on surveys on the relevance and applicability of their course to their future
7	Proportion of students who report a sense of belonging to the Institute
8	Proportion of students participating in extra-curricular group activities
9	Ratio of spaces for private study, physical spaces for collaborative learning and social interaction, and facilities (Canteen, reading rooms, common rooms, playgrounds)
10	Proportion of students who have actively engaged with resources (e.g. by completing online training module) on appropriate and respectful use of information and communication technologies.
11	Proportion of students who have actively engaged with resources (e.g. by completing online training module) on anti-discrimination policies and complaint processes for redressing offensive, intimidating or discriminatory behaviour
12	Involving students in developing and delivering wellbeing activities at key points during the academic calendar such as orientation, interim assessment, events and other activities.
13	Organising and promoting mental health training for student leaders involved in peer support programs
14	Involving students in data collection and evaluation of wellbeing programs and activities

Institutional Enablers Check list for Mental Wellbeing.

A ready reckoner for evaluating the implementation and integration of mental health wellbeing is suggested by the researchers. The discussions that emerged from the focus groups and the questionnaires helped the researchers develop the **Institutional Enablers Check list for Mental Wellbeing.**

#	Enablers of Mental well being	Status Report *	Remarks**
1	Curricula and co-curricular offerings that build students' self-knowledge (e.g. values and character strengths) so they are better able to make decisions and identify career pathways consistent with their values, interests, and strengths		
2	Proportion of subjects/units embedding overall knowledge and skills for mental wellbeing (e.g. building resilience, embedding mental health literacy, autonomy, self-management, employability competencies)		
3	Number of Extra Curricular, Co-Curricular and Cultural Events conducted		
4	Awareness programs on information sharing regarding Anti- Ragging Policy, POSH, Gender Sensitization and Women development activities		
5	Availability of Grievance Redressal Cell and awareness amongst students		
6	Availability of Anti- Ragging Committee and awareness amongst students. To be verified through Anti-Ragging undertaking		
7	Availability of mentors and mentorship programs. Faculty mentors and guides for different activities		
8	Non-Discriminatory and transparent Placement policies		
9	Formation of Mental wellbeing club and regular activities under the club		
10	Formation of CSR & Green club and regular activities under the club		
11	Formation of student council, with active representation of co-curricular, CSR and Women development representatives		
12	Sports and cultural events conducted for promoting overall well being		

#	Enablers of Mental well being	Status Report *	Remarks**
13	Clear guidelines for Internal Compliant Committee, related to grievance across all activities in the HEI		
14	Academic Leadership and Advocacy for Mental wellbeing Program		

**Should have dates of meeting and review of such courses and curriculum*

***Reasons for justification of any activities implemented or not implemented*

The checklist includes all Institutional processes for development and review of mental health policies, and of targets and indicators related to student mental wellbeing within all aspects of institutional life, including responsible data collection and analysis so that policies and actions are based on accurate and appropriate information about students' needs, interests, circumstances, and health.

REFERENCES:

Dybdah R and Lien L (2018) “Mental health is an integral part of the sustainable development goals”, <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/324749556>, DOI:[10.15761/PMCH.1000104](https://doi.org/10.15761/PMCH.1000104)

Batra S (2023) Spiritual triple bottom line framework- A phenomenological approach , <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0970389623000320>
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iimb.2023.04.006>

Ahmed A (2019) Mental Health problem and Sustainable Development in India, Indian Journal Of Community Health / Vol 31 / Issue No 02 / Apr - Jun 2019

Votruba N & Eaton J (2014) The importance of global mental health for the Sustainable DevelopmentGoals,

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25405815/>,DOI: [10.3109/09638237.2014.976857](https://doi.org/10.3109/09638237.2014.976857)

Thornicroft G & Patel V (2014) Including mental health among the new sustainable development goals, <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25145688/> DOI: [10.1136/bmj.g5189](https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g5189)

[.https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/toi-editorials/chronicles-of-death-suicide-is-a-rising-trend-in-india-including-among-the-young/.6](https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/blogs/toi-editorials/chronicles-of-death-suicide-is-a-rising-trend-in-india-including-among-the-young/.6) December 202

CHAPTER 5

ROLE OF FACULTY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION

Prior to the 1980s, the working conditions of the employees was very different. The employees of the olden times were strictly led by the principles of loyalty and commitment to the organization. Highly dedicated employees endowed loyalty to the organization, and in reciprocation for that commitment, they were offered lifetime employment in their workplace. In the 1980s, with increased global competition, employers were demanded to be more flexible in their deployment of employees. Plants were closed due to economic conditions, unrest and political motives, and then firms again reopened in countries where wages were lower. As business became global, leaders looked-for more regulation by government, regarding wages, salaries and benefits to employees so that they can compete effectively. Employees of the organisation soon understood that loyalty was no longer compensated by life -long job, and it is a futile endeavour to create a commitment in the workplace. As change is very dynamic and volatile in the global environment, the old school convention of loyalty and faithfulness had become invalid. Thus, the employee engagement movement reached as a tactic to resolve this problem. The experts claim that engaged employees do more; therefore, to get more out of less, the logic would be that managers simply need to engage their people. What started as a movement, became a culture and practice in the world of human resource management

After liberalization of the Indian economy, the impact of privatisation, economic changes and international markets had put pressure on all functions of the organizations (Bhatnagar , 2007; Budhwar, et al, 2026) There is requirement amongst the managers to build capacities, competencies and capabilities. With the overall competition, retaining and attracting good talent has become a challenge. Employee engagement is key to the retention of talent in an organization. Over the last few years, several studies related to the management of talent has been conducted, but mostly in developed countries and in a corporate context. Even within the employee engagement framework, very little has been done on teaching faculty and staff in colleges and universities. [1]

There is an immense need to study employee/ faculty engagement in the education sector. The literature study on employee engagement shows very little study in faculty engagement and motivation. Faculty engagement and motivation is possible if organizations, i.e. colleges and

institutes provide the teachers with a passion to work and an engaging ambience which their performances and gives them a continuous satisfying work experience.

The selection and recruitment of teachers also plays a significant role in employee engagement and work satisfaction. It is therefore very important to have proper selection and recruitment of faculty members, fitting the job requirement, experience, and knowledge. Engaged teachers in a college or university will provide better learning outcomes for students and demonstrate better role- efficacy.

A study by Bailey et al 2015; suggests that high work engagement leads to lower voluntary turnover Having engaged employees results in better faculty and student feedback and better stakeholder satisfaction. Another very important aspect of employee engagement is on-the-job training. The recent concept of inductee teachers helps in providing teachers with training opportunities of learning, research and self-development, thereby contributing more towards work productivity and employee engagement. [2]

The questions that arise are:

- What is the organizational responsibility to attract and keep creative, zealous, and thriving employees who make organizations flourish?
- Which working conditions and environments motivate employees to be engaged, to work with commitment, take risk to do something more and different, and withstand difficult situations?

There has been a considerable change in the learning organizational structure. The traditional learning organizational structures greatly rely on direct control of the management, autonomy and adherence to economic principles of cost reduction, efficiency, and cash flow has taken a leap and the major focus in current organizations is on the smooth and judicious management of human capital, ie the teachers in this case. Currently, learning organizations expect their employees to be proactive and exhibit initiative, collaborate smoothly with their peers, take responsibility for their own professional development, and to be committed to high quality teaching and research standards.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To measure the engagement level of faculty in Higher Education Institutions
- 2) To study the demographic variables along with Vigour, Dedication, and Absorption of faculty in HEIs
- 3) 3). To find out the engagement level between men and women faculty members.

- 4) To analyze the effect of work experience on the level of employee engagement
- 5) To analyze the effect of monthly salary on the level of vigour, dedication and absorption of faculty members.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Employee Engagement is a fundamental concept in the effort to understand and describe, both qualitatively and quantitatively, the nature of the relationship between an organization and its employees. An "engaged employee" is defined as one who is fully absorbed by and enthusiastic about their work and so takes positive action to further the organization's reputation and interests.

Conceptual Background

Burnout Antithesis Approach (2011) by Shuck's, identified four main approaches to defining engagement, which can also be utilized when exploring measures of engagement: [13, 18]

The Needs-Satisfying Approach:

Needs satisfying approach, in which engagement is the expression of one's preferred self in task behaviours. William Kahn (1990) provided the first formal definition of personnel engagement as "the harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performance. [3, 4]

Burnout antithesis approach, in which energy, involvement, efficacy are presented as the opposites of established "burnout" constructs: exhaustion, cynicism and lack of accomplishment.

The Satisfaction Engagement Approach:

Satisfaction-engagement approach, in which engagement is a more technical version of job satisfaction, evidenced by The Gallup Company's own Q12 engagement survey. [6]

The Multidimensional Approach:

There is a clear distinction maintained between job and organizational engagement, usually with the primary focus on antecedents and consequents to role performance rather than organizational identification.

Four Approaches

Needs-Satisfying Approach

William Kahn (1990) provided the first formal definition of personnel engagement as “the harnessing of organization members' selves to their work roles; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performances”.

The ‘Needs-Satisfying Approach’ Measure developed from the theoretical propositions and empirical findings of Kahn’s (1990, 1992) work on “psychological engagement”. The construct captures the physical, cognitive, and emotional aspects of one’s preferred self that are simultaneously employed and expressed when performing one’s job role. Rich et. al. (2010) developed the job engagement measure aimed to map onto Kahn’s (1990) three-factor conceptualization. The final 18-item questionnaire scale was validated via a sample of 245 US fire-fighters. [5]

Description of the Scale: Rich et al’s (2010) -JES

The scale of employee (Job) engagement has 17 items based on three dimensions. Dimension Physical Attribute is represented by five questions. Dimensions Emotional and Cognitive have

six questions each. Making the questionnaire based on 17 Items. Participants rated their levels of employee engagement on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). [7]

1. I work with intensity on my job. (physical)
2. I exert my full effort to my job. (physical)
3. I devote a lot of energy to my job. (physical)
4. I try my hardest to perform well on my job. (physical)
5. I strive as hard as I can to complete my job. (physical)
6. I am enthusiastic about my job. (emotional)
7. I feel energetic about my job. (emotional)
8. I am interested in my job. (emotional)
9. I am proud of my job. (emotional)
10. I feel positive about my job. (emotional)
11. I am excited about my job. (emotional)
12. At work, my mind is focused on my job. (cognitive)
13. At work, I pay a lot of attention to my job. (cognitive)
14. At work, I concentrate on my job. (cognitive)
15. At work, I focus a great deal of attention on my job. (cognitive)
16. At work, I am absorbed in my job. (cognitive)
17. At work, I devote a lot of attention to my job. (cognitive)

Expected Findings

After using above scale the analysis may reveal the physical, cognitive, and emotional level of employee engagement with the concerned job role. The findings may indicate the varying of the engagement level due to demographic profiles. So these items were compared with the UWES and further research was conducted.

Burnout Antithesis Approach:

Schaufeli et al. (2002) conceptualizes “work engagement” as the positive opposite of psychological burn out. They defined engagement as “a positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption” (pg. 74). This perspective refers to feelings of vigour (e.g. energy), dedication (e.g. enthusiasm), and absorption (e.g. feeling immersed).

The **Utrecht Work Engagement Scale** was developed by Schaufeli et al. (2002) assesses three dimensions: vigor, dedication, and absorption. There are six questions for vigor and absorption and five questions for dedication, creating a total of 17 questions. Participants rate their levels of employee engagement on a 7-point Likert scale (0 = Never to 6 = Always/Every day).

Description of Scale:

1. At my work, I feel bursting with energy. (vigor)
2. I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose. (dedication)
3. Time flies when I'm working. (absorption)
4. At my job, I feel strong and vigorous. (vigor)
5. I am enthusiastic about my job. (dedication)
6. When I am working, I forget everything else around me. (absorption)
7. My job inspires me. (dedication)
8. When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work. (vigor)
9. I feel happy when I am working intensely. (absorption)
10. I am proud of the work that I do. (dedication)
11. I am immersed in my work. (absorption)
12. I can continue working for very long periods at a time. (vigor)
13. To me, my job is challenging. (dedication)
14. I get carried away when I'm working. (absorption)
15. At my job, I am very resilient, mentally. (vigor)
16. It is difficult to detach myself from my job. (absorption)
17. At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well. (vigor)

Expected Findings

After using above scale the analysis may reveal the state of mind of respondents in terms of energy, enthusiasm and feeling of immersion. The findings may indicate the varying of the engagement level due to demographic profiles.

1. Determinants of Employee Engagement

Employee engagement is appositve fulfilling work related state of mind that is characterized by vigour, dedication and absorption.

1. Vigour- Vigour indicates high levels of energy at work, resilience both physical and mental, time and strategy invested in actual work and high level of perseverance even during difficult times. Vigour has a positive influence on employee performance. An individual with vigour will do good things for the organization that would contribute towards bigger success.
2. Dedication- Dedication at work refers to the disciplined behavior of an employee at work. A dedicated employee will always follow rules, comply with the policies, work hard to meet goals and take initiatives to initiate new things. This individual takes pride in his or her responsibilities, duties and feels important and meaningful in the organization. In the role efficacy scale the individual goes from role entering to role centering.
3. Absorption- Absorption happens in employee engagement when an individual has perseverance and can absorb the instructions, roles and job descriptions better. The individual is more concentrated on work and escapes surrounding disturbances. The individual is not a clock watcher and stays focused in fulfilling his job obligation

4. METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology

The present study is a descriptive study and is based on primary data. Primary data has been collected from colleges and institutes of higher education in Maharashtra, Chennai, Kolkata & Delhi. A structured questionnaire was adopted for collecting primary data through questionnaire method and in few cases, wherever possible through interview method, to collect in- depth information of the education system. Secondary data and literature study is taken from published articles, journals, periodicals, and research papers.

Hypotheses of the Study

- 1) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Vigour’ with reference to Gender.
- 2) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Dedication’ with reference to Gender.
- 3) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Absorption’ with reference to Gender.

- 4) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Vigour’ with reference to Teaching Experience.
- 5) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Dedication’ with reference to Teaching Experience.
- 6) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Absorption’ with reference to Teaching Experience.
- 7) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Vigour’ with reference to Monthly Salary.
- 8) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Dedication’ with reference to Monthly Salary.
- 9) Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘Absorption’ with reference to Monthly Salary.

Research Design

The philosophical foundation of this quantitative study builds upon the theory of knowledge regarding validity, scope, and method. The study adopted a positivism approach. The study focuses on theory testing in the context of teaching fraternity. The descriptive design was adopted with the use of demographic variables.

Sampling Framework

The Stratified Random technique was adopted to select the sample from the universe. All the teachers were considered as the ‘Universe’ of study. The study was undertaken only for higher education college teachers. The college teachers from all specializations of Management, Interdisciplinary Education, were included while considering the importance of NEP 2020 in near future. Teachers from social sciences were included in the study to focus on interdisciplinary education. Moreover, the age group of samples were kept 30 years and above. Around 100 questionnaires were shared with respondents through google form and some personal interviews were also held to get in-depth understanding. Around 72 questionnaires complete in all aspects were considered for further analysis. However, sufficient care was taken by the researcher to avoid chance error, sample frame errors, non-response errors and misinterpretation errors.

Tool Description

Construct of Employee Engagement

An "engaged employee" is defined as one who is fully absorbed by and enthusiastic about their work and so takes positive action to further the organization's reputation and interests.

Employee Engagement Measures

There are four main approaches to explore measures of engagement namely –

- a) Needs-Satisfying Approach' Measure developed by Kahn's (1990, 1992) by focusing on "psychological engagement". Rich et. al. (2010) developed the job engagement measure aimed to map to Kahn's (1990) three-factor conceptualization.
- b) Burnout Antithesis Approach: Schaufeli et al. (2002) conceptualizes "work engagement" as the positive opposite of psychological burn out. They developed **Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES)** to assess three dimensions: vigor, dedication, and absorption. There are six questions for vigor and absorption and five questions for dedication, creating a total of 17 questions.
- c) Satisfaction Engagement Approach: The scale was developed by Gallup Company for commercial purposes.
- d) The Multidimensional Approach: This approach resulted in a 16-item measure to assess cognitive, behavioral, and emotional engagement developed by Andel et al. (2018).

The tool used for the present study was **Utrecht Work Engagement Scale (UWES)** developed by Schaufeli et al. (2002). The 17 items used a five-point rating scale was chosen, ranging from 1= Strongly disagree, 2= Disagree, 3= Can't say, 4= Agree and 5= Strongly agree. A comparison of the questionnaire of UWES and Physical, emotional and cognitive scale was done, as stated above, the scale, shows the factors and attributes that contributes to faculty engagement in Interdisciplinary Higher Education.

Question 1, 4, 8, 12, 15 and 17 -----Vigour Scale

Question 16, 14, 3, 6, 9 and 11-----Absorption Scale

Question 2, 5, 7, 10 and 13 ----- Dedication Scale

The five items of Physical Dimension Attribute matches with the six items of Vigour Dimension Attribute. The Emotional and Cognitive dimensions have much similarity with Dedication and Absorptions.

The tool consists of -

1. Personal information of respondents on age, gender, salary levels, and years of experience.
2. Other factors contributing to the engagement level the faculty members, such as vigour, dedication, absorption.

Reliability of the Tool

Table : II – Cronbach Alpha Score

SR. No.	Sub-Variable	Number of Statements	Cronbach Alpha
1	VIGOUR	6	0.872
2	DEDICATION	5	0.892
3	ABSORPTION	6	0.852

Cronbach's alpha is a measure of the extent to which the group of questions are related to one another. The measurement accuracy of the tool is good as Cronbach Alpha is above 0.8.

Data Interpretation

The following range will be used for the data interpretation to indicate the level of engagement (Objective 1). **Table : III Range of Level of Engagement**

SR. No.	Sub-Variables	No of Items	Five-Point Scale	Range	Interpretation of Mean value
1	Vigour	6	1 - Strongly Disagree To 5 – Strongly Agree	6.00 to 14.00	Low Level Vigour
				14.01 to 22.00	Moderate Level Vigour
				22.01 to 30.00	High Level Vigour
2	Dedication	5		5.00 to 11.66	Low Level Dedication
				11.67 to 18.33	Moderate Level Dedication
				18.34 to 25.00	High Level Dedication
3	Absorption	6		6.00 to 14.00	Low Level Absorption
				14.01 to 22.00	Moderate Level Absorption
				22.01 to 30.00	High Level Absorption

5. ANALYSIS OF DATA

The first part of this section was indicated by Frequency table for demographic details of the respondents. Further Mean and standard deviation was shown to designate the level of sub-variables of engagement. Inferential Statistics used for the testing of hypotheses.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Table No : 1- Age of the Respondents

Categories	Coding	Frequency	Percent
30-40	1	24	33.3
40-50	2	17	23.6
50-60	3	27	37.5
60 and above	4	4	5.6

N= 72

Graph 1: Histogram; Age of Respondents

The respondents were in the Age group of 30 to 65 years and minimum age was considered as 30 years for the study as maturity and understanding of career goals is more focused for employees above 30. 65 years was taken as the maximum age limit as that is the retirement age for teachers/professors in higher education. The total number of respondents were divided according to the class interval of 30- 40, 40- 50, 50- 60 and 60- 70 years. The class interval is continuous, where the upper limit of the previous class is counted in the next class, as shown in the table above. The maximum number of respondents was in the age group 50-60 year, i.e. 27 respondents, followed by 24 respondents in the age group of 30-40 year, 17 respondents in the age group of 40- 50 and only 4 respondents in the age group of 60 and above. It is

understood therefore that most faculty members in the age group of 50 -60 year has taken the survey as they are interested in knowing better the employee engagement process and be effective in guiding the junior faculty.

Table No. : 2- Teaching Experience of the Respondents:

Categories	Coding	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 years	1	15	20.83
5 to 10 years	2	11	15.28
10 to 15 years	3	16	22.22
15 to 20 years	4	16	22.22
20 and above	5	14	19.44

N = 72

Graph No: 2 Total Experience

The number of years for teaching experience is considered from below 5 years to 20 years and above. The class interval is taken as 5 years and is continuous in nature. Since the maximum number of respondents were in the age group of 50 -60 year, the class 10 years to 15, 15 years to 20 and 20 years and above has the maximum frequency, i.e., most respondents are in that experience group.

Table No: 3 -Gender Profile

Categories	Coding	Frequency	Percent
Male	1	45	62.5
Female	2	27	37.5

N =72

Graph No- 3 Gender Profile

Of the total respondents, 45 were men and 27 were women teachers.

Table No: 4-Monthly Salary of the Respondents:

Categories	Coding	Frequency	Percent
Less than 1 lakh	1	14	19.4
1 lakh to 1.5 lakhs	2	19	26.4
1.5 lakhs to 2 lakhs	3	22	30.6
Above 2 lakhs	4	17	23.6

N = 72

At the beginning of the study, it was mentioned that due to the increase in faculty pay packages and implementation of sixth and seventh pay commission, the salary levels are high. When organizations pay higher salaries the expectations from the faculty members are also high. The maximum number of respondents are seen in the salary bracket between Rs 1 Lakh to 2 lakhs.

Graph No: 4 Salary Statistics

Descriptive Statistics

The total sum score, mean and the standard deviation has been worked out for all statements and sub-variables - ‘Vigour’, ‘Absorption’ and ‘Dedication’ presented below-

Table No 5 : Sum, Mean and Standard Deviation of Items

Sr. No.	Statements	Sum	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	At my work, I feel bursting with energy. (vigor)	293	4.07	.924	High Level
2	I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose. (dedication)	297	4.13	.963	High Level
3	Time flies when I’m working. (absorption)	289	4.01	.942	High Level
4	At my job, I feel strong and vigorous. (vigor)	296	4.11	.972	High Level
5	I am enthusiastic about my job. (dedication)	283	3.93	1.012	High Level
6	When I am working, I forget everything else around me. (absorption)	296	4.11	1.001	High Level
7	My job inspires me. (dedication)	286	3.97	1.007	High Level
8	When I get up in the morning, I feel like going to work. (vigor)	295	4.10	1.009	High Level
9	I feel happy when I am working intensely. (absorption)	307	4.26	.993	High Level
10	I am proud of the work that I do. (dedication)	288	4.00	.888	High Level
11	I am immersed in my work. (absorption)	274	3.81	.959	High Level
12	I can continue working for very long periods at a time. (vigor)	275	3.82	.983	High Level
13	To me, my job is challenging. (dedication)	267	3.71	.971	High Level
14	I get carried away when I’m working. (absorption)	274	3.81	.882	High Level
15	At my job, I am very resilient, mentally. (vigor)	268	3.72	1.051	High Level
16	It is difficult to detach myself from my job. (absorption)	272	3.78	.996	High Level
17	At my work I always persevere, even when things do not go well. (vigor)	293	4.07	.924	High Level

Source- prepared

Table No : 6-Sum, Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables

Sr. No.	Variable	Sum	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	Vigor (6 Items)	1679.00	23.3194	4.41134	High Level
2	Dedication (5 Item)	1467.00	20.3750	4.07479	High Level
3	Absorption (6 Items)	1698.00	23.5833	4.47450	High Level

N =72

From above table it is observed that respondents indicated higher level mean for all three variables of employee engagement.

Inferential Statistics

A) Gender and Vigour, Dedication & Absorption

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean Vigour, Dedication and Absorption level scores with reference to Gender.

For testing the hypothesis, the Independent ‘t’ test was computed for men and women

Table No.: 7 Sum, Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables Gender Wise

Variables	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Vigour	Male	45	24.0889	4.49152
	Female	27	22.0370	4.03334
Dedication	Male	45	21.0222	3.95135
	Female	27	19.2963	4.12138
Absorption	Male	45	24.3333	4.41588
	Female	27	22.3333	4.36771

Table No- 8 Independent Samples Test

Independent Samples Test	
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means

		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
VIGOUR	Equal variances assumed	.941	.335	1.948	70	.055	2.05185	1.05333	-.04895	4.15266
DEDICATION	Equal variances assumed	.001	.979	1.766	70	.082	1.72593	.97746	-.22356	3.67542
ABSORPTION	Equal variances assumed	.104	.748	1.868	70	.066	2.00000	1.07063	-.13530	4.13530

Analysis of the Findings

Three variables of employee engagement were computed by using ‘Independent t’ test wrt men and women. The sig. value was more than 0.05 for all three sub-variables. Therefore, there was no significant difference between men and women in terms of their vigor, dedication and absorption for their organization and work profile. Hence, the null hypothesis can be retained. It can be concluded that all HEI teachers of Management from Maharashtra have **similar level** of engagement for their organization as well as profession.

Table No.: 9 Hypotheses

Sr. No.	Hypotheses	Significant Or No-significant Difference
1	There is no significant difference in the mean Vigour level scores with reference to Gender.	No-significant Difference
2	There is no significant difference in the mean Dedication level scores with reference to Gender.	No-significant Difference
3	There is no significant difference in the mean Absorption level scores with reference to Gender.	No-significant Difference

Table No. : 10- Hypotheses Testing

Sr. No.	Hypotheses	Significant/ No-significant Difference
1	There is no significant difference in the mean Vigour level scores with reference to Work Experience.	No-significant Difference
2	There is no significant difference in the mean Dedication level scores with reference to Work Experience	No-significant Difference

3	There is no significant difference in the mean Absorption level scores with reference to Work Experience	No-significant Difference
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B) Teaching Experience and Vigour, Dedication & Absorption

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean scores of 'Vigour', 'Dedication' and 'Absorption' level with reference to Teaching Experience.

Table No.: 11- Sum, Mean and Standard Deviation of Variables Teaching Experience Wise

Variables	Teaching Experience	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Vigour	Less Than 15 Years	42	23.2143	4.52384
	More Than 15 Years	30	23.4667	4.32103
Dedication	Less Than 15 Years	42	20.0714	4.08682
	More Than 15 Years	30	20.8000	4.08867
Absorption	Less Than 15 Years	42	23.2381	4.45470

Table No. 12: Independent Samples Test

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
VIGOUR	Equal variances assumed	.366	.547	-.238	70	.813	-.25238	1.06159	-2.36965	1.86489
DEDICATION	Equal variances assumed	.022	.883	-.746	70	.458	-.72857	.97712	-2.67738	1.22023
ABSORPTION	Equal variances assumed	.155	.695	-.772	70	.442	-.82857	1.07266	-2.96793	1.31078

Table No. : 13- Hypotheses Testing

Sr. No.	Hypotheses	Significant/ No-significant Difference
1	There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘ Vigour ’ level with reference to monthly salary.	No-significant Difference
2	There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘ Dedication ’ level with reference to monthly salary	No-significant Difference
3	There is no significant difference in the mean scores of ‘ Absorption ’ level with reference to monthly salary.	No-significant Difference

6.CONCLUSION

What has been observed in the study is that faculty members are not individual workers, working in silos, they are integrated into a system that has students, management, institutions, and other stakeholders. Faculty engagement is required to realize higher levels of student learning attainment. What had happened earlier was the decoupling of teaching role and research role of faculty, more because remuneration for faculty was low. So, it was not expected of faculty to accomplish both the roles. But in the new career prospects under Sixth and Seventh pay commission, teaching, research, and institution building has been integrated. With increased faculty engagement, there are strategic collaborations between faculty and support professionals, thereby bringing more faculty engagement in academic institutions. The positivity of faculty engagement is transmitted to the students, thus making learning more student oriented.

A very important observation of the study was the reason for the change in the engagement pattern of faculty members/teachers in the HEI. What has been discussed and seen during the research interview is that the faculty have expressed the support of the senior management and academic leaders in their meaningful contribution. Teachers mentioned that they expect respectful treatment and two- way communication for better engagement and performance. Hence HODs, Principals, Directors, and Deans, along with the Management have a big role to play in the effective employee engagement. High- quality leadership, proper governance and ethical practices in academic institutions can contribute towards better employee engagement. During the in-depth interview, many faculty members mentioned that the behavior of the senior academic leaders have impact on faculty engagement. Due to the increased role of technology in teaching, young faculty /teachers are adept in it and reverse mentoring is on the rise. While senior academic leaders share knowledge and research skills with young faculty members, they in turn teach the senior members technology-based learning. This has improved the faculty

engagement in HEIs. The academic environment is more civil and there is less rudeness as compared to earlier times.

REFERENCES

1. Aryee S, Budhwar P, Chen Z (2002) “Trust as a mediator of the relationship between organizational justice and work outcomes: Test of a social exchange model *Journal of Organizational Behaviour* 23 (3) pp 267-285
2. Bailey, C., Madden, A., Alfes, K. and Fletcher, L. (2015), “The meaning, antecedents and outcomes of employee engagement: a narrative synthesis”, *International Journal of Management Reviews*, pp. 1-23. doi: 10.1111/ijmr.12077.
3. Bakker, A.B., and Demerouti, E. (2007), “The job demands resources model: state of the art”, *journal of Managerial Psychology*, Vol. 22 No. 3, pp. 309-328.
4. Bakker, A.B., and Demerouti, E. (2014), “Job demands-resources theory”, in Chen, P.Y. and Cooper, C.L. (Eds), *Work and Wellbeing: Wellbeing: A Complete Reference Guide*, John Wiley & Sons, Vol. 3
5. Bakker B A & Schaufali B W (2006) , “Defining and measuring work engagement: Bringing clarity to the concept”,
<https://www.wilmarschaufeli.nl/publications/Schaufeli/326.pdf>, accessed on 24 /8 /2023
6. Blizzard R (2004) “ Engagement Vs Satisfaction Among Hospital Teams,
[https://New Gallip.com/poll/10903](https://NewGallip.com/poll/10903), accessed on 25/8/ 2023
7. Rich, B.L., Lepine, J.A., et al. (2010) Job Engagement: Antecedents and Effects on Job Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*, 55, 617-635.
<https://doi.org/10.5465/AMJ.2010.51468988>, accessed on 25/8/2023
8. Bechtoldt, M.N., Rohrmann, S., de Pater, I.E. and Beersma, B. (2011), “The primacy of perceiving: emotion recognition buffers negative effects of emotional labor”, *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 96 No. 5, pp. 1087-1094. doi: 10.1037/a0023683
9. Bertalanffy, L.V. (1968), *General System Theory: Foundations, Development, Applications*, Braziller, New York, NY.
10. Bititci, U.S. (2015), *Managing Business Performance: The Science and The Art*, John Wiley & Sons, Chichester.
11. Breevaart, K., Bakker, A., Hetland, J., Demerouti, E., Olsen, O.K. and Espevik, R. (2014), “Daily transactional and transformational leadership and daily employee engagement, *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, Vol. 87 No. 1, pp. 138-157, doi: 10.1111/joop.12041.

12. Clapon.P (2016) “Employee Engagement, HR Info graphics, HR Trends and Workplace Happiness”
13. Gould-Williams, J. and Davies, F. (2005), “Using social exchange theory to predict the effects of HRM practice on employee outcomes”, *Public Management Review*, Vol. 7 No. 1, pp. 1-24.
14. Hsieh, C.C, and Wang, D.-S. (2015), “Does supervisor-perceived authentic leadership influence employee work engagement through employee-perceived authentic leadership and employee trust?” *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 26 No. 18, pp. 2329-2348. doi: 10.1080/09585192.2015.1025234
15. Johnson, H.T. and Kaplan, R.S. (1987), *Relevance Lost*, Harvard Business School Press, Boston, MA.
16. Shuck, B., Twyford, D. Jr, Reio, T.G. and Shuck, A. (2014), “Human resource development practices and employee engagement: examining the connection with employee turnover intentions”, *Human Resource Development Quarterly*, Vol. 25 No. 2, pp. 239-269
17. Muduli, A., Verma, S. and Datta, S.K. (2016), “High performance work system in india: examining the role of employee engagement”, *Journal of Asia-Pacific Business*, Vol. 17 No. 2, pp. 130-150.
18. Neely, A. (1999), “The performance measurement revolution: why now and what next?” *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*, Vol. 19 No. 2, pp. 205-228.
19. Smith M, Bititci U (2017), “Interplay between performance measurement and management, employee engagement and performance” *International Journal of Operation and Production Management*, Vol 3, No 9, pp 1207-1228, Emerald Insight
20. Simons, R. (1994), “How new top managers use control systems as levers of strategic renewal”, *Strategic Management Journal*, Vol. 15 No. 3, pp. 169-189.
21. Shuck, B. and Wollard, K. (2010), “Employee engagement and HRD: a seminal review of the foundations”, *Human Resource Development Review*, Vol. 9 No. 1, pp. 89-110, doi: 10.1177/ 1534484309353560
22. Weiner, N. (1948), *Cybernetics*, Wiley, New York, NY.
23. www2.deloitte.com/us/en/insight/talent -2020 Surveying the talent paradox from the employee – perspective. Html

CHAPTER 6

ACADEMIC LEADERSHIP IN HIGHER EDUCATION

1. INTRODUCTION:

The effectiveness of our higher education system depends on effective and vibrant teachers with knowledge of Academics, Assessment and evaluation, Pedagogy, Research Culture, and Innovation in teaching & learning. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 specifies that the “most important factor in the success of higher education institutions is the quality and engagement of its faculty [1-6].

A career in higher education is very rewarding, whether it is in teaching, research, or administration. It is important that faculty members work on developing leadership qualities and skills. Effective leadership in academics happens only when the faculty develops all aspects that comprise teaching, research, innovation, networking, and administration. Any academic leader, who has risen through different ranks of teaching cadre, i.e., Assistant Professor (Lecturer), Associate Professor (Reader), and then full Professor will always be a hands-on academic administrator. No matter whatever specific duties and responsibilities a teacher has, leadership skills and practices should be used to be an effective leader. A good academic leader should be able to take major decisions for an educational institution and fulfil the vision and mission of the Institution.

Teachers shape the future of the nation. The teaching pedagogy as prescribed by NEP is determined by the training provided to the teachers, their empowerment to implement outcome-based education and the motivation given to teachers through career advancement, salaries and incentives, to reach the desired standards.

Faculty members should constantly upgrade their knowledge through their research and participation in knowledge upgradation. It is only the engagement strategy of the faculty and the Institution, that can make a vibrant learning organization.

The authors propose to conduct a study to explore the broader theme of ‘Understanding and Transforming Higher Education’ with the following factors that can contribute to a focused National Education Policy framework:

- (1) Changing paradigm in higher education
- (2) Higher order learning
- (3) New age learning
- (4) Technology & its tools
- (5) Simulations and experiential learning
- (6) Examination reforms
- (7) Role of communication in faculty engagement

Management education is an important branch of higher education in India and has a high impact on India’s economic growth. It has proven to be very successful in providing much-needed qualified and skilled professional manpower. The NEP’s focus on multidisciplinary education in management institutions suggested future policy implementation and a road map for management education [1-6]. Unlike other disciplines, management schools do not have an intake of bachelor students from their disciplines only. The postgraduate courses offered by the management institutes in India have interest of students from diverse backgrounds. These institutes provide holistic education within multiple fields of management. Almost 82 % seats in postgraduate management courses are occupied by students from diverse educational backgrounds. Thus, management schools have a highly multidisciplinary student intake compared to other disciplines.

Business schools by their very nature are different from other educational institutions and thus need to be looked at differently by policy makers. Management education institutions have a different model than general/ or other academic programs. Management education is highly linked to the requirements of the industry and the coursework can be flexible. Globally and in India management schools are focused on postgraduate programs, while accepting students from all disciplines.

It is heartening that the Ministry of Human Resources has come out with the National Education Policy also referred to as New Education Policy, NEP 2020. The policy is aimed to address and plug the various loopholes in the current education system. NEP 2020 mentions the need for entrepreneurship education and industry-institute partnerships at various levels of the academic hierarchy. The NEP puts emphasis on research, innovation, entrepreneurship, and professional education, especially about the curriculum with learning outcomes like knowledge, skills, self-confidence and entrepreneurial initiatives [1-6].

Business schools have been providing professionally trained graduates to Industry 4.0 to fulfil its requirements. What's turning out to be more important is the approach in the face of complex challenges and uncertainties. The administrative abilities of leaders and managers are put to the test only in complex situations. When companies are redefining their purpose, B-Schools should redefine their pedagogy. To rethink work, workforces, and workplaces, the role of higher education and B- schools, is imperative.

Throughout time, academic institutions have sought to respond to the demand of changing and evolving environmental conditions and structural changes in higher education. The roles of the leaders within the institutions have changed to solve different functional needs at the institute level. The role of an academic leader is managing through information, monitoring, disseminating knowledge, delegating, designing, discussing, making, distributing, and managing staff, acting directly or indirectly. Economic and administrative responsibilities, human resource management and development, internal and external cooperation, networking, research collaboration and many other roles have evolved, more so in the last 10 years. Today's B- School faculty must spend time outside of academic and create a positive impact on career growth.

This research studies the awareness and preparedness of outcome-based education with a focus on inputs, processes, and output. The study uses Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs for Employee Engagement in Management Education. Finally, the study proposes strategies to improve faculty engagement in Management Institutes. [13]

Goals are formulated by employees themselves and in consultation of superiors. Goals are mental images of preferred outcomes to which an individual is committed and moves ahead to realize it (Fishbach & Ferguson, 2007) [8]. Faculty sometimes feel as if they're adrift in the world. Though they put in a lot of effort, probably they don't seem to get anywhere meaningful. Goal setting requires the acquisition of knowledge, and it requires an individual to organize his/her time and resources so that they can make the most of their life. While setting a goal an individual makes a commitment on the achievement of realizing the goal; the commitment should rest on the understanding that the individual has the capability of achieving the goal; and that s/he will behave over and over again with that commitment (Cialdini, 2009). Taking the essence of SMART goals, making goals realistic and achievement, an individual's knowledge about his/her strengths is very important. A purposeful goal setting illuminates the requirements of the organization and paves the way for the employee to approach the goal. A personal understanding of one's strengths and weaknesses helps to identify the most realistic goals based on the individual's current situation and helps to recognize goals that should be kept on hold for the future. Strengths are the set of an individual's natural abilities that the individual perceives as good at performing. As the individual is more aware of his strengths, he will be better positioned to set achievable goals.

Individuals who consciously know and use their strengths are closer to their set goals and are more capable of delivering successful results. Focusing on already-known strengths helps an individual become more focused on which he/she can excel. Knowing their strengths will help individuals to understand how to apply them to the job they do; this is where it gets linked with performance. Looking at performance, strengths-based development involves three stages: identifying the talent, matching with self-perception bringing in necessary behavioural change (Clifton & Harter, 2003) [9].

The study addresses the challenges in outcome-based education and how knowledge and training of NEP can improve outcome-based education.

2. OBJECTIVES :

- (1) To evaluate the understanding of NEP and OBE amongst faculty members and academic leaders
- (2) To explore the factors affecting teaching and learning in higher education.
- (3) To identify and evaluate the attributes of Academic Leadership for academic, administrative, and research & extension activities.
- (4) To discuss a conceptual model with the required attributes and qualities for a Role model/Super academic leader.
- (5) To study the role of academic leadership in implementing outcome-based education in higher education.

3. METHODOLOGY :

The empirical analysis is based on the data collected from 53 academic leaders from 53 different B-schools. To have better results the study has collected data from different regions in India, covering East, West, North, and South

Data is collected through a data triangulation approach. For this purpose, structured questionnaires were used, telephonic interviews of the sample, and Focus Group Discussions with members of the senior cadre were conducted.

The study employed different methods of data collection, preliminary interviews, and focus group discussions to yield the parameters on which a structured questionnaire was prepared. After deciding on the constructs of the scale, indicator items were prepared with the assistance of the experts in the field. Statistical analysis is done to assess the awareness and application of NEP 2020 in Management Education.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS :

A total of 53 survey complete survey forms were received. Of this, 58 % were faculty members from Private B- Schools and 42 % were from Government and Deemed University. The respondents were from different locations, like, Bangaluru, Chennai, Delhi, Jaipur, Kashmir, Kolkata, Mumbai, Odisha, Pune, and Telangana.

About 26.4 % were in the age group of 30- 40 years, 35.8 % were in the age group of 41- 50 32.1 % were in the age group of 51-60 years, and 5.7 % in the age group of 60 years and above. About 34 % of the respondents were with 20 years of experience and above. 26.4 % had 15-20 years of experience, 17 % of the respondents had 15- 20 years of experience and 22.6% with 10 years of experience. More than 52.8 % of the respondents firmly believe that outcome-based education is a shift from context-based learning and 51% is of the opinion that outcome-based education is more focused on curriculum structures and processes. For fulfilling the NEP objectives of outcome-based education, 54.7 % of the academic leaders strongly agree that proper manpower planning and training is needed and 62.3 % of the respondents agree that the autonomy of teachers is important for setting goals and standards to meet the learning outcomes. However, 47.2 % of the respondents agree that training through workshops, with respect to NEP should be provided for better implementation.

In the focus group interview, the following suggestions were provided by the senior academics

- (1) The NEP structure should focus on the Indian Knowledge System in the curriculum.

- (2) Education should focus on innovation and value-based learning outcomes.
- (3) NEP should make the structure more inclusive and accept diversity.
- (4) A detailed road map and planning are needed for better implementation.
- (5) Proper guidelines for teachers and institutions should be there for a proper understanding of credit transfer and gap year.
- (6) The most important suggestion was to upgrade the facilities and modernize the system for which regular quality checks and internal quality assessments should be conducted.

The Academic Leaders mentioned that faculty engagement is important to;

- (1) Identify the strengths and weaknesses of faculty.
- (2) Identify core strength areas to improve upon.
- (3) Help in setting goals and formulating action plans.
- (4) Facilitate in generating alternative plans to address the concern.

This above analysis matches with the Attribute study and Employee Engagement in higher education. Employee engagement is an attitude that employees gradually form about their organization and the work they do. It is the responsibility of the employer to create a culture of open communication, learning and development, work-life balance, recognition, and rewards [10-12]

Major job attitudes are job satisfaction, job involvement, and organizational commitment. All the three will increase the overall performance of the organization.

Table 1- Analysis of Attribute and Impact

S. No.	ATTRIBUTE	IMPACT
1	Job Resources: Physical, Social and Organizational aspects of the job	Work environment that offers many resources foster the willingness to dedicate one's effort and abilities. The task will be completed successfully
2	Performance Management: Is a tool used to quantify the efficiency or effectiveness of action. Organizational control. Organizational control and management control theories view organizational as dynamic entity.	An employee can perform better only with meaningful work engagement supported by both technical control and social control systems
3	Training and Development: Effective training and development, employee engagement and empowerment are important factors to reduce turnover and increase in productivity.	When employees are nominated for training and development, they perceive themselves to be valued by the organization and to be reciprocating with more vigour, dedication and absorption.
4	Career Development Opportunities: Career development is an important aspect of employee engagement. All that is learnt in training is used in career development.	Satisfaction of growth needs depend on a person finding the opportunity to be what he or she is most to achieve in career. This improves the level of engagement.
5	Incentive: Compensation or remuneration is an important attribute for employees. Attractive compensation comprises of pay appraisals, promotions, bonuses, and rewards. It becomes essential for management to present acceptable stands on remuneration and recognition, if they wish to achieve a high level of engagement	Only bringing up the pay and incentive package, without proper HR policies will not encourage employee engagement. Incentives should be supported with structured career progression policies.

5. APPLYING MASLOW'S HIERARCHY OF NEEDS TO EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS:

Fig.1: Adapted from Maslow's Hierarchy- Model developed by Researchers [13]

The focus group discussion and primary interview with the academic leaders helped to design the application of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs to Employee Engagement in Higher Education [13]. The objective is to understand why the level of engagement is low and develop strategies to motivate faculty members for better engagement.

The disengaged stage of an employee can be compared with the survival stage of Maslow's hierarchy of needs. This is at the entry level, where the faculty is new in the job, and is learning the tricks of the trade, the faculty wants to focus more on the job, to have a permanent, tenured job, hence is less engaged in other related activities, other than teaching. This is the mistake many new teachers make; it is this contribution that ultimately brings the success to teaching and improves faculty engagement.

The faculty then progresses to a level where he/she seeks security and from disengagement gradually starts moving towards low level of engagement. This phase is a transition phase and without much cognizance of the faculty, it moves to a stage of belongingness to the organization, where the employee is almost engaged. It is very important therefore that the academic leader takes effort in making the transition from disengaged to almost engaged. The teacher and the senior management should therefore identify the deficiency or inadequacy in a new faculty and motivate them through training and development. One must satisfy lower-level deficit needs before progressing to meet higher level growth needs. All work environments follow the same dynamic since its human being who are represented everywhere.

Micromanagement and autocratic management styles are the reasons for low engagement levels. Continuous bickering, fault finding, and interference discourages the employee to engage whole heartedly in the organization. The employee just hangs-in there only for salary. Here the Institutions and students stand to lose as the faculty is not committed to the vision and mission of the organization.

In level three, the employee gradually finds a sense of belonging to the organization and is now interested in the career growth path. The work performance, vigour and dedication gradually improve. The final stage is, self- actualization, when the employees find the meaning of success in the organization. The perception, that the organization fulfils all needs, starting from economic to psychological (growth needs) is the phase when faculty is committed to the organization and delivers the desired results.

It's therefore very important for the faculty to know the level of their performance and areas in which they need improvement. Performance improvement helps the organization to meet its goals and objectives. Performance counselling is a very important activity that helps employees to know themselves better. It has been observed that employee engagement increases with performance counselling.

6. CONCEPTUAL FINDINGS:

6.1 Attributes of Academic Leadership for Academics in HEIs:

A comprehensive list of anticipated attributes for academic leadership in higher education institutions is given in Table 2. These attributes emerged from the personal interviews with the academic eaders

Table 2: Expected attributes for academic leadership for Academic activities of HEIs

S. No.	Key Attributes	Description
1	Visionary Leadership	Possession of the ability to articulate a convincing vision for the academic development and growth of the institution.
2	Strategic Planning	Competence in formulating long-term plans that support the objectives of the organization and adjust to the ever-changing nature of education.
3	Innovative Thinking	Promoting an innovative culture in research, education, and administrative procedures.
4	Collaborative Skills	Promoting cooperation between academic staff, students, faculty, and other stakeholders in order to attain academic success.
5	Effective Communication	Strong communication abilities to express ideas, motivate people, and have productive conversations.
6	Ethical Decision-Making	Maintaining the highest moral standards while making decisions, making sure that everything is transparent and equitable.
7	Empowering Faculty Development	Providing faculty with opportunities for professional development to improve their research and teaching techniques.
8	Promotion of Diversity and Inclusion	Dedication to creating a welcoming, inclusive, and varied learning environment that honours all viewpoints and backgrounds.
9	Adaptability and Resilience	Capacity to negotiate obstacles and developments in postsecondary education, modifying tactics to suit changing requirements.
10	Data-Informed Decision-Making	Incorporating data analytics and evaluation instruments to guide and enhance educational initiatives and guidelines.

11	Student-Centric Approach	Putting a high priority on student achievement by offering a supportive learning environment, resources for students, and chances for development.
12	Resource Management	Effectively overseeing financial resources, physical spaces, and new technology in order to meet academic objectives.
13	Quality Assurance and Accreditation	Ensuring that academic programs adhere to accreditation organizations' mandates and quality standards.
14	Global Perspective	Embracing internationalization initiatives and developing worldwide alliances to raise the academic status of the institution.
15	Crisis Management Skills	The ability to manage difficult circumstances and handle crises while upholding the institution's image and integrity.
16	Advocacy and Leadership Development	Defending the interests of the university while assisting and mentoring upcoming academic leaders.

These attributes collectively contribute to effective academic leadership, guiding higher education institutions toward excellence and relevance in a dynamic educational landscape.

6.2 Attributes of Academic Leadership for Administration Activities:

A detailed list outlining the anticipated attributes of academic leadership specifically focused on administrative activities within higher education institutions is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Expected attributes for academic leadership for administrative activities of HEIs

S. No.	Key Attributes	Description
1	Organizational Management Skills	Competence in supervising departments, managing intricate administrative systems, and streamlining processes to increase productivity.
2	Financial Acumen	The capacity to plan and oversee budgets, obtain financing, and make wise financial decisions in order to further the objectives of the organization.
3	Policy Development and Implementation	Establishing and carrying out rules that respect academic goals and guarantee adherence to laws and guidelines.
4	Strategic Resource Allocation	Setting priorities for needs, allocating resources wisely, and maximizing resource use across departments.
5	Technology Integration	Embracing technology developments to increase business efficiency, optimize data management, and expedite administrative procedures.
6	Risk Management	Recognizing any hazards and creating plans to reduce them in order to maintain the stability and sustainability of the organization.
7	Human Resources Leadership	Putting in place efficient HR procedures, encouraging a healthy workplace environment, and making sure that employees are treated fairly.
8	Change Management	Overseeing and directing shifts and modifications in organizational frameworks, promoting flexibility and reducing interference.

9	Collaborative Partnerships	Building connections with other institutions, government bodies, business partners, and external stakeholders in order to promote cooperation and win-win outcomes.
10	Facilities and Infrastructure Development	Directing the construction and upkeep of campus buildings to make sure they satisfy the changing requirements of academic programs and student life.
11	Compliance and Accreditation Management	Ensuring adherence to legal criteria and managing the accreditation procedures for different educational programs.
12	Data Governance and Analytics	Putting in place mechanisms for data governance, using analytics to guide administrative choices, and improving institutional efficacy.
13	Crisis Response and Preparedness	Creating thorough backup plans and procedures to deal with emergencies or unanticipated circumstances that impact administrative operations.
14	Environmental Sustainability Initiatives	Promoting sustainability initiatives inside the organization and putting eco-friendly procedures into facilities and administrative processes.
15	Transparent Communication and Reporting	Keeping lines of communication open and transparent in order to inform interested parties about decisions and developments made by the administration.
16	Continuous Improvement and Evaluation	Putting in place systems for continual assessment, gathering input, and executing process enhancements in administration.

These attributes are vital for effective leadership in administrative roles within higher education institutions, ensuring smooth operations and support for the academic mission.

6.3 Attributes of Academic Leadership for Research, Publication, & Extension Activities:

A comprehensive list outlining the anticipated attributes of academic leadership in research, publication, and extension activities within higher education institutions in the following Table 4:

Table 4: Expected attributes for academic leadership for Research, publication & extension activities of HEIs

S. No.	Key Attributes	Description
1	Research Vision and Strategy	Creating and sharing a clear vision for research projects that are in line with the objectives and mission of the organization.
2	Strategic Planning for Research	Creating strategic plans to find funding sources, promote an innovative and inquisitive culture, and advance research aims.
3	Mentorship and Support for Researchers	Provide tools, mentorship, and advice to academic staff and students who are conducting research.
4	Promotion of Interdisciplinary Research	Fostering multidisciplinary research projects and encouraging cross-disciplinary cooperation to address difficult issues.

5	Grant Acquisition and Management	Obtaining grants and resources for research, successfully managing spending plans, and guaranteeing adherence to financial specifications.
6	Publication and Knowledge Dissemination	Assisting in the spread of knowledge by facilitating the publication of research findings in respectable journals and venues.
7	Intellectual Property and Technology Transfer	Encouraging the transfer of technology, the commercialization of research results, and the defence of intellectual property rights.
8	Quality Assurance in Research	Putting in place procedures and safeguards to guarantee the excellence, morality, and conduct of research projects.
9	Extension and Community Engagement	Creating collaborations, outreach programs, and projects that use research results to address societal issues and involve the community.
10	International Collaboration in Research	Promoting partnerships with international partners to improve research capacities, exchange knowledge, and address global concerns.
11	Research Infrastructure Development	Investing in cutting edge buildings, labs, and technology to assist cutting edge research projects.
12	Metrics and Impact Assessment	Evaluating the effects of research endeavors on academics, society, and business through the use of metrics and assessment instruments.
13	Continual Professional Development in Research	Providing opportunities for continuous training and development so that researchers can keep up with new approaches and advancements in social science and technology.
14	Promotion of Research Ethics and Integrity	Maintaining a culture of academic integrity in research techniques and making sure that ethical standards are followed.
15	Evaluation and Recognition of Research Achievements	Putting in place systems for honouring and compensating exceptional contributions to publications and research.
16	Flexibility and Adaptability in Research Agenda	Recognizing new trends and modifying research goals to take advantage of opportunities and difficulties of the modern world.

These qualities are essential for academic leadership since they stimulate creativity, support publication, extension, and research activities while also advancing knowledge in higher education.

6.4 Academic Administrator as Role Model/Super Academic Leader :

"Role model" or "Super Academic Leader" describes an academic administrator who has high values for administrative innovation, academic innovation, and research & extension innovation. A "Super Academic Leader," also known as an Academic Role Model Leader, is a person who possesses extraordinary abilities and attributes in a variety of fields. The required attributes and qualities for Role model/Super academic leader is listed below:

(1) Visionary Leadership:

Their mission for significant research and extension initiatives, academic quality, and administrative efficiency is both obvious and exciting. Their strategic choices are informed by this vision, which also encourages others to pursue innovation.

(2) Holistic Innovation Champion:

A culture of innovation is actively encouraged and supported in all facets of the organization, including academic, administrative, and research/extension. They set an exemplary example by promoting innovation, creativity, and forward-thinking methods.

(3) Collaborative Approach:

A Super Academic Leader is someone who loves teamwork, cultivates an atmosphere that welcomes many viewpoints, and promotes multidisciplinary collaboration. They encourage collaboration, joint ventures, and information exchange across institutions and departments.

(4) Strategic Thinker and Executor:

They successfully convert their vision into workable plans by putting into practice creative policies, programs, and initiatives that promote administrative effectiveness, academic expansion, and significant research and extension.

(5) Continuous Learner and Mentor:

They demonstrate an unwavering commitment to learning, keeping abreast of emerging trends, technologies, and approaches. Additionally, they actively mentor and assist staff, instructors, and students in their pursuit of innovation and professional development.

(6) Ethical and Inclusive Leadership:

They preserve the greatest moral standards, guaranteeing integrity, fairness, and openness in all facets of academics. They also promote inclusion, equity, and diversity, creating a climate in which everyone is treated with respect and worth.

(7) Resourceful and Adaptable:

Super Academic Leaders are adept at resource management, using it to fund creative academic initiatives, smooth administrative operations, and significant research & extension. They adjust to shifts, transforming obstacles into chances.

(8) Communication Mastery:

They are excellent communicators; they can engage stakeholders, clearly state their goal, and promote candid discussion. Their ability to communicate effectively inspires, encourages, and wins support for creative projects.

(9) Results-Oriented and Impact-Driven:

They put a strong emphasis on measurable outcomes and use research and extension activities to gauge how their initiatives are affecting academic progress, administrative efficiency, and the larger community.

(10) Risk-Taker and Resilient Leader:

They embrace experimentation and the ability to learn from mistakes, and they are not afraid to take measured risks. Because of their resilience, they can overcome obstacles and disappointments and keep moving in the direction of their objectives.

(11) Global Engagement and Advocacy:

They actively interact with international partners, promoting cross-border cooperation and speaking out on behalf of the institution's interests internationally.

All of these qualities are combined to create a Super Academic Leader who is an inspiration to others in the academic community and at their own institution. They drive transformation, inspiring others to embrace innovation and excellence in academia, administration, and research & extension.

(12) Integration of SDGs into academic curriculum:

Academic leaders of Higher Education Institutions (HEI), play an important role in promoting United Nations-Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs) through the curriculum and

learning experiences of the students. HEI can drive change and participate in dissemination of SDGs.

7. STRATEGIES SUGGESTED TO IMPROVE EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION :

(1) Culture and Perspective: The first and foremost thing required for improving employee engagement is changing the organizational culture and perspectives towards employee engagement activities. Organizations will have to facilitate and promote commitment of employee well-being and an accessible and transparent HR Policy.

(2) Rewards and Recognition: Every individual need reward and recognition in the form of incentives, pay, promotion, felicitation, and acknowledgment of faculty contribution towards the institution. This is a big factor in determining employee engagement.

(3) Role of Senior Leaders and Management: What has been discussed and seen during the research interview is that the faculty have expressed the support of the senior management and academic leaders in their meaningful contribution. Teachers mentioned that they expect respectful treatment and two- way communication for better engagement and performance. Hence HODs, Principals, Directors and Deans, along with the Management have a big role to play in effective employee engagement. High-quality leadership, proper governance, and ethical practices in academic institutions can contribute towards better employee engagement. During the in-depth interview, many faculty members mentioned that the behavior of the senior academic leaders has an impact on faculty engagement. Due to the increased role of technology in teaching, young faculty /teachers are adept in it, and reverse mentoring is on the rise. While senior academic leaders share knowledge and research skills with young faculty members, they in turn teach the senior members technology-based learning. This has improved faculty engagement in HEIs. The academic environment is more civil and there is less rudeness as compared to earlier times.

(4) Structured Appraisal Forms: With a structured Appraisal Form shared by Higher Education authorities, things have become more transparent, and the faculty gets due credit for all activities, starting from research, teaching, institution building, social contributions and participation in knowledge sharing events. This is the reason for high faculty engagement in HEI.

(5) Attributes of Academic Leadership: The attributes of Academic Leadership for academic, administrative, and research & extension activities are identified, analyzed, and evaluated in the study. These recommendations can be considered for excellence in academics.

(6) Role Model/Super Academic Leader: A conceptual model with the required attributes and qualities for a Role model/Super academic leader in academic leadership, administrative leadership, and research and extension activities leadership is also suggested. To support this, certificate courses, workshops and training are required. Such workshops can be organized at state level, by universities or by group of institutions.

8. CONCLUSION :

Diversity of thinking is much needed in a business school, academic leaders and faculty must be able to develop a corporate outlook and mindset in students and this is achieved by making the academic industry goal-oriented. It can further be added here that setting goals like research, classroom teaching, institution building and administrative responsibilities for faculty members in an agile business school is to update knowledge in management education, keeping abreast with the recent trends and requirements, and also competing for better ranking and quality management. It has also been observed that faculty handling varied roles as teachers

as well as administrators make better academic leaders and develop the ability to tackle difficult situations, problems, and knowledge to achieve individual and institutional goals.

The subject of faculty engagement has started to be seen and talked about by both big and small institutions, yet implementation is still a grey area. The first step towards faculty engagement is to know what motivates people, what drives their actions, and what translates into productivity, performance, and loyalty to the organization. Clapton, P (2016) [7] in her study on employee performance suggested three engagement drivers.

First, is the Management and Leadership driver; based on the report of Employee Engagement Trends of Quantum Workplace- 2016, the two most important drivers are (i) leaders' commitment and (ii) Trust in the leaders to set the right path always. Employees reported high levels of trust in their leaders leading to higher employee engagement. Employees feel engaged when they are valued and their efforts are recognized. The second important driver is meaningful work. Meaningfulness of the job can be thought of as the feeling that one's job contributes to society as a whole, a specific community, a cause, and many more. The mission and vision statements are essential and provide guidance to all stakeholders. Therefore, the effectiveness of communicating the mission and vision to the employees is equally important. The Deloitte Talent 2020 series surveyed 560 employees across every major industry and global region. According to this report, 42 % of respondents believe their job doesn't make good use of their skills and abilities, hence retaining them could be a challenge. Career progress and challenging profiles are the top factors influencing career decisions. Meaningfulness of the job was also identified as employees' engagement driver in SHRM's 2016 Employee Job Satisfaction and Engagement Report. The third and equally important driver is the relationship with co-workers. One of Gallup's Q 12 reputed survey statements proved that relationship with co-workers have proven to be essential for all workplaces. Research shows that employees' relationships with co-workers and supervisors will increase the psychological meaningfulness and employee engagement. Positive relationships with co-workers can foster a sense of loyalty, camaraderie and moral support. These bonds boost overall results and productivity. Individuals who feel personally meaningful will be motivated to give 110% at work.

There are several factors like job resources, performance measurement, training and development, career development, incentive factors at job, compensation benefits, work environment, company culture, and many more that drive employee engagement. Together these factors form an intricate system that motivates people to give their best. It is felt that employees should be encouraged to talk openly and engage in giving and receiving feedback and bringing new projects to the table. Making a difference toward a purpose that is larger than one individual or organization offers a sense of fulfilment to employees. With a structured Appraisal Form shared by Higher Education authorities, things have become more transparent, and the faculty gets due credit for all activities, starting from research, teaching, institution building, social contributions, and participation in knowledge-sharing events. This is the reason for high faculty engagement in HEI [14-15].

What has been discussed and seen during the research interview is that the faculty has expressed the support of the senior management and academic leaders in their meaningful contribution. Teachers mentioned that they expect respectful treatment and two-way communication for better engagement and performance. Hence HODs, Principals, Directors, and Deans, along with the Management have a big role to play in effective employee engagement. High-quality leadership, proper governance, and ethical practices in academic institutions can contribute towards better employee engagement. The attributes of Academic Leadership for academic, administrative, and research & extension activities are identified, analyzed, and evaluated. A conceptual model with the required attributes and qualities for a Role model/Super academic leader is also described.

REFERENCES :

- [1] India's National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, <https://indianexpress.com>
- [2] National Education Policy 2020, Ministry of Human Resource Development, Government of India, www.niepid.nc.in/nep-2020.pdf, accessed on 02/08/2020
- [3] National Education Policy (2000). What are education experts saying about the new National Education Policy." www.indiatoday.in/education-today
- [4] Salient- Features of NEP 2020, www.hindustantimes.com, accessed on 10/08/2020
- [5] Salient Features of NEP 2020, UGC, www.ugc.ac.in, accessed on 02/08/2020
- [6] The National Education policy 1968: <https://www.education.gov.in>
- [7] Clapon, P. (2016). Employee Engagement, HR Info graphics, HR Trends and Workplace Happiness. The HR and Employee Engagement Community. <https://gethppy.com/employee-engagement/the-top-3-employee-engagement-drivers>.
- [8] Fishbach, A. & Ferguson, M. (2007). The Goal Construct in Social Psychology. *Social Psychology of Education*, 1(1) 334-352. DOI 10.1007/BF02333407
- [9] Clifton, D. O., & Harter, J. K. (2003). Strength's investment. Positive organizational scholarship. (pp. 111-121). San Francisco
- [10] Estacio, D. & Carbera, W. (2018). Job Attitude as a Factor on Employee Performance. *International Journal of Research & Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, Volume 8, Issue 3 . <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354857782>
- [11] Judge, T. A., & Kammeyer-Mueller, J. D. (2012). Job attitudes. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 63, 341–367. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-120710-100511>
- [12] Padmavathy, N. (2018). Impact of Workers Attitude and Job Satisfaction “, *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts , IJCRT* 1807287, www.icrt.org, 387-391.
- [13] How Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Applied to Employee Engagement (2020) <https://blog.clearcompany.com/how-maslows-hierarchy-of-needs-applies-to-employee-engagement>
- [14] Kay, J., & Tumwet, E. (2015). The Role Of Staff Counseling In Promoting Work Engagement And Productivity: A Case Of Kabarak University. *Kabarak Journal Of Research & Innovation*, 3(1), 65-73. Retrieved From <https://Ojs.Kabarak.Ac.Ke/Index.Php/Kjri/Article/View/33>.
- [15] Irmayanti F, Yusman Y & Maurhea S (2022). The Effect of Employee Counselling Approach In Measuring Employee Engagement on Employee Loyalty to Employee Bank, BTN. *European Journal of Psychological Research*, 9(2), ISSN 2057-4746

CONCLUSION

Business schools have been providing professionally trained graduates to industry 4.0 to fulfil its requirements. What's turning out to be more important is the approach in the face of the complex challenges and uncertainties. The administrative abilities of leaders and managers are put to test only in complex situations. When companies are redefining their purpose, B- Schools should redefine their pedagogy. To rethink work, workforces and workplaces, the role of higher education and B- schools, is imperative. Skills required in 2019 are not the same anymore. Often questions on problem solving and perseverance are asked during recruitment. The answer to such questions is possible only when the students have exposure to industry related activities and problem-solving skills, integrated with the programme and the course.

The technological disruption that the world is currently undergoing is unprecedented. This has led to a radical transformation in the education ecosystem. According to the Organization for Economic development (OECD) , “Future of Education and Skill Project (2030)”, we need to replace old education standards with an educational framework with 21st century skills of creativity, critical thinking, communication and collaboration. This can't be achieved by simply moving teaching from white board to online. What is needed is radically transforming the way knowledge is disseminated and skills acquired. Along with knowledge and skills, what is needed is attitude and value to thrive in and shape the future to a more global workplace.

The FICCI- EY report, 2021, has also studied the well-reasoned and bold reformation steps suggested by NEP 2020. The NEP focuses on disruptive changes by taking into cognizance the issues of equitability, inclusivity, accessibility, exploratory and experimental, all ingredients required for transforming Education 4.0 and beyond.

The education sector was among the initial impact bearers of SARS COV2 Virus (COVID-19) lockdowns. Even when the economy moved towards staggered unlocking, it remained among the last to open. Probably the online and digital classes initiated during the pandemic is already a crucial component suggested by NEP. As the NEP mentions, the future of education in a decade time from now on, will be focussed on enhancing the student experience and ensure that teaching and learning functions smoothly to deliver quality experience. Curriculum and pedagogy could be revised to incorporate formal, informal, physical and digital elements to enhance learning. Education models focussed on blended and interdisciplinary learning, that integrates technology access, teaching pedagogy and assessment methods can deliver better quality education.

In a country where 50 % of the population is below the age of 25 years, it's the onerous responsibility of the Government to provide better education, training and skill development to enable the youth for a proper livelihood. Our literacy rate of 74 % and in some states at 100% doesn't fulfil the requirement of skill needed by industry.

Our focus was earlier on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy. In the current situation the focus should move to employability skill. With this background, certain changes in the NEP are proposed with the vision for balanced education. The focus of NEP 2020 has been, employability and entrepreneurship. Which education, other than Business Management studies delivers the two? Definitely, management education is the way forward, albeit, with the changes required.

A new age student demands courses offering flexibility and multidisciplinary options. Affordable learning solutions with a quick return on investment and career counselling support is what is needed in Higher Education Institutes (HEI). A paradigm shift is inevitable to cater to the needs of growing new age student. Education and health care are always perceived in India, as a not-for-profit enterprise. While some health care facilities and few business schools charge market driven fees, most of them still struggle to breakeven. Under such circumstances B-Schools compromise on quality of inputs. The education system has evolved over the centuries in response to social, economic and technology innovations which in turn are impacted by the evolution in education system. During Education 1.0, faculty, curriculum and pedagogy have remained flexible, research, partnership, infrastructure, governance and leadership were almost non-existent. For Education 2.0 Partnership was flexible and other parameters like faculty, curriculum, research, leadership were rigid. However, during Education 3.0, Research and Infrastructure were both flexible. In 2005, there were 1 billion internet users worldwide. In 2011 the number increased to 2 billion users, which further increased to 3.5 billion internet users in 2016 and 4.7 billion users in 2021. Internet penetration in India stood more than 45% in 2021, new age learners have more exposure to online material and flexibility of learning. While in Education 1.0 student was a passive recipient, in Education 2.0, communication and collaboration started growing. Education 3.0 was more student-centric, making education 4.0 more innovative and co-creative. Education 4.0 puts the learners at the centre of the eco-system and empowers them to structure their learning paths with outcome. With the quickly changing employment and global ecosystem, it is becoming increasingly important that learners not only learn but learn how to learn. Education must therefore move towards less content and more towards learning how to think critically and solve problems, how to innovate, adapt and absorb new materials in novel and changing fields. Adaptability, agility, multi-disciplinary knowledge and people management skills command a huge premium in handling consumer behaviors, marketing, supply chain management. Education must build character, enable learners to be ethical, rational, compassionate and flexible, while at the same time prepare the future managers for gainful employment. The National Education Policy 2020 lays particular emphasis on the development of the creative potential of each individual, in all its richness and complexity. It is based on the principle that education must develop not only cognitive skills but also higher order critical thinking. The policy aims at building a global best education system rooted in Indian ethos and aligned with the principle of higher order learning, thereby transforming India into a global knowledge super-power. Under the current education system, most HEIs get stuck at level 1, level 2 and level 3 of learning, i.e., remembering, understanding and applying. Any fixed hour exams can assess only the lower order learnings. For higher order learning like analyzing, evaluating and creating, hands-on learning experience is needed, which can be addressed through course projects, mini projects, minor projects, capstone projects, entrepreneurship and industry interactions.

Business Schools must focus more on research, research that is relevant, has rigor and process. Research creates new knowledge and students get oriented to research, which they anyways will have to practice later in their career. The relevance of the B-Schools will come in developing skills that are fundamental to the changes in the economy. In the 90's it used to be IT skills (Information Technology) today we need Digital Skills. When we say Digital skills, we mean skills needed as digital disruptors and digital integrators. Amazon from a digital

disruptor has now become a digital integrator. The skills required to function in Industry 4.0 are different from the skills required for Industry 2.0. Business Schools have to re-orient their objectives towards, (i) Technology and (ii) Leadership.

Business Management educators, therefore, should give top priorities for some courses like, industry immersed curriculum blended with new- age electives like , Business Analytics, Decision Science, Design Thinking and Disruptive strategy. Unique industry mentorship programs mentored by industry experts in real life projects is ideal under the current learning situation. The future of work has already arrived. A key point to note is that the tasks where human are set to retain their competitive advantage, are managing, advising, decision making, reasoning, communicating and interacting. The focus of HEI should be on developing individuals for these roles. When the winds of change are blowing some build shelters and some build wind mills. Trust and credibility are the two pillars of any business, Higher Education Institutions should be able to build trust and credibility.

LIST OF PUBLICATION FROM THE REPORT:

1. Ancient Education and its Relevance in Modern Education
2. Modern Multidisciplinary Education
3. Effect of Extracurricular and Co-Curricular Activities on Students’
Development in Higher Education
4. Employee Engagement in Higher Education
5. Academic Leadership in Higher Education
6. The sixth paper on “Mental Well Being in Higher Education:
Implementation and Integration Strategies”, is submitted for a conference
and publication post conference.